

A Real-Time VR Rendering Survival Guide for Human Scientists

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Abstract

Virtual reality (VR) has emerged as a transformative tool for experimental research in the human sciences, yet the development of immersive and high-fidelity virtual environments presents significant technical challenges. Here we present a comprehensive guide for researchers which prior experience in VR rendering seeking to improve the realistic rendering techniques and optimization of VR scenarios. We detail the core principles of real-time rendering—from the intricacies of the graphics pipeline and shader workflows to the management of draw calls and performance optimization—while addressing the unique demands of rendering. This guide aims to equip researchers with the knowledge to create visually compelling and performance-optimized virtual experiments. We aim to bridge the gap between advanced rendering methodologies and experimental design, thereby empowering human science researchers to implement robust and reproducible VR environments.

During the preparation of this work, the authors used large language models like ChatGPT in order to improve the writing and clarity of the paper. After using these tools/services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Introduction

Over the past decades, virtual reality (VR) has increasingly attracted researchers from various disciplines in the human sciences, including neuroscience, psychology, clinical research, human-computer interaction (HCI) and education (Blascovich et al., 2002; Bohil et al., 2011). This interest surged notably with the introduction of high-fidelity but low-cost consumer head-mounted displays (HMDs) such as the Oculus Rift and HTC Vive. The possibilities VR offers in the lab are immense, allowing for the design of complex, ecologically valid experiments that remain meticulously controlled. For example, in psychological research, VR enables the simulation of realistic social interactions, offering an unprecedented level of control over variables such as timing, gaze direction, and spatial positioning (Pan & Hamilton, 2018). In clinical neuroscience, VR can replicate scenarios where patients navigate or interact with stimuli in ways that would be difficult or even impossible to recreate in a traditional lab setting (Riva et al., 2007; Rizzo & Koenig, 2017).

Despite VR's promising potential to enhance research in the human sciences, developing virtual environments demands skills and techniques that typically lie outside the training of most researchers in these areas. This challenge is particularly pronounced concerning 3D rendering and the creation of high-fidelity graphics. While researchers in disciplines like HCI, neuroscience, or psychology often have a solid foundation in programming for purposes such as creating stimuli or analyzing data, expertise in 3D graphics is rarely part of their education.

This knowledge gap is especially critical because VR rendering is inherently complex and computationally intensive. Without a thorough understanding of rendering principles, even simple or non-photorealistic scenes can result in significant performance issues. Consequently, many scientists switch into VR research without the necessary tools and knowledge to fully leverage its capabilities, thereby restricting both the scope and the effectiveness of their experiments.

Some scientists have proposed a shortcut for developing high-fidelity VR experiments with limited development experience. Instead of building the entire scenario from scratch, one approach is to modify commercially available VR games, such as Oculus Rift's *Echo Arena* (Monti & Aglioti, 2018)). However, this method relies on the availability of modifiable games, particularly those that provide easy-to-use modding tools. While some games provide modding tools developed by their creators—such as Epic Games' VR shooter *Robo Recall*, which includes a custom version of Unreal Engine—modifying other games can be significantly more challenging. Furthermore, this approach still requires a solid understanding of game engines and VR rendering to implement the experimental routines. It also often forces researchers to adhere closely to the game's existing themes and mechanics—thereby restricting the experimental environment to settings that may not align with their research objectives (for example, attempting to create a relaxation-focused experiment within a violent first-person shooter environment)—or undertake extensive modifications to tailor the game to their specific needs. The considerable time and diverse expertise required for such drastic changes can make this method less practical compared to developing a new scene

from ground up, which allows researchers to precisely design the virtual environment to match their research questions.

However, does this mean researchers must create all their assets—the building blocks of a virtual environment, including 3D models, textures, sound effects, and animations—from scratch? While building everything from the ground up offers maximum flexibility to tailor virtual environments to specific research needs, it is rarely necessary to reinvent the wheel every time. Fortunately, numerous online resources provide ready-made assets. These assets can be purchased from commercial stores like the Unity Asset Store or FAB; or can be sourced from free libraries like AmbientCG.com or Polyhaven.com. Especially for realistic scenes, it is relatively easy to find models of all kinds of everyday objects. In principle, researchers can construct entire virtual environments using only pre-existing assets, without having to create a single one themselves. For the remainder of this guide, we will focus on integrating the assets for the visual rendering into a game engine, utilizing its tools to create realistic and optimized VR scenarios, rather than focusing on the process of creating these assets from itself.

Although many tutorials cover game development in engines such as Unity (Unity Technologies, 2025) and Unreal Engine (Epic Games, 2025), the various aspects of development are often scattered across different sources and authors, rather than offering a comprehensive overview of the entire process from start to finish. This fragmentation makes it challenging for beginners in 3D graphics difficult to know where to begin and which processes or tasks are most relevant to their goals. This guide aims to help researchers improve the visual fidelity, visual realism, and rendering performance of their VR scenarios.

Furthermore, there are important differences between developing commercial games and designing research experiments. A guide focused specifically on research scenarios can help concentrate on aspects most relevant to researchers, which often differ from those in commercial game development.

Commercial game developers aim to create marketable products, which often requires novel and visually striking environments to attract and retain players. In contrast, researchers typically prioritize controlled and valid settings that are suited to studying specific phenomena. While game developers may struggle to attract interest if a sequel looks too similar to its predecessor, researchers face no such pressure. In fact, reusing virtual environments from previous studies can be beneficial—especially when conducting multiple experiments on the same phenomenon—as it enhances comparability across studies.

Also, the typical scale of commercial VR games differs from that of typical research scenarios. While games often feature expansive environments and prolonged gameplay, research scenarios are usually much smaller in scope, both in terms of the size of the virtual environment and the duration of use. Of course, there are exceptions where research demands large-scale virtual environments (see e.g., Nezami et al., 2021; Wiesing et al.,

2024)—but these remain relatively rare. Most experiments do not require more than a single room or a small outdoor scene, which simplifies design and performance optimization.

Another key difference in performance optimization is that game developers—especially those targeting PC—must ensure their games run smoothly across a wide range of hardware platforms. Since players may use anything from high-end machines to low-spec systems, developers need to implement scalability options, such as toggles for rendering features or adjustable texture resolutions, to accommodate different performance levels. In contrast, research experiments typically run on a fixed set of hardware within a controlled laboratory environment. This allows researchers to optimize specifically for a single device, eliminating the need for scalability options and greatly simplifying the optimization process. And because the hardware and performance parameters remain constant, there is no excuse for performance issues—developers can and should test the scenario in advance until it is certain to run smoothly in every session.

About this guide

This guide aims to provide a high-level overview of what is needed to develop custom, realistic VR scenarios that are visually compelling and perform efficiently, even on standalone HMDs like the Oculus Quest. It is designed to guide human scientists through essential concepts and techniques of realistic real-time rendering in VR, rather than serving as a beginner-friendly, step-by-step tutorial.

Readers should already have a fundamental familiarity with Unity or Unreal Engine, including basic tasks such as scene setup, asset handling, and interface navigation. While the guide explains key concepts and techniques, it does not include detailed implementation instructions. These specifics can readily be found in official Unity or Unreal documentation and existing tutorials, which often provide more comprehensive explanations than the scope of this guide allows.

Think of this guide as similar to a restaurant guide, which introduces various restaurants, describes their type of cuisine, gives an idea of price ranges, and provides practical tips like how early one might need to reserve a table. However, it does not list the exact menu items, as these frequently change and are best found directly through the restaurant's website or current online resources. Similarly, this guide aims to highlight important rendering concepts and their relevance, rather than detailing every technical step, encouraging readers to seek the most accurate and up-to-date implementation instructions independently.

A significant emphasis throughout this guide is put on understanding the performance impact of different rendering aspects and effects. The core idea is to make readers constantly aware that real-time rendering operates within the constraints of limited system performance, and every addition to the scene will reduce available resources to some degree. Therefore, the best strategy for developing well-optimized VR scenarios is to always estimate how each additional element might affect the system's performance. This guide aims to encourage this performance-aware mindset from the outset of the development process, enabling researchers to create optimized virtual environments perfectly tailored to support their research objectives.

The focus on visual realism is largely driven by our practical experience, as most of our VR development work has focused on creating lifelike virtual environments. However, even though this guide focuses on visual realism, many of the aspects of 3D rendering discussed are similarly relevant to stylized and minimalistic environments.

Designed to be broadly applicable across different game engines, specific examples mostly focus on Unity, as this is the most used engine within research in general and also the engine used in our own research. However, researchers using other engines, such as Unreal Engine, need not be discouraged. The fundamental principles of real-time rendering—including the concepts and techniques for achieving visual realism and maintaining performance—are largely the same across platforms. When relevant, we will highlight some of the key differences between Unity and Unreal Engine, however, this is not intended to be exhaustive.

Although the guide aims to remain hardware agnostic, it will focus to some degree on standalone VR systems and in particular Meta Quest devices. This focus stems from our substantial experience with these devices, whereas our experience from other hardware manufacturers is more limited. Concentrating on a specific engine and hardware platform allows us to provide concrete examples without overextending the scope of this guide. Nonetheless, the information presented should be transferable to other systems in most cases, even when specific examples pertain to Unity and Meta Quest.

Furthermore, standalone VR devices are increasingly popular among both researchers and casual users due to their mobility and ease of use. However, these devices have significant hardware limitations compared to high-end PC setups. Therefore, it makes sense to focus on optimization for these lower-end systems, as techniques that ensure efficient rendering on standalone devices will invariably also perform well on more powerful gaming PCs, though the reverse is not necessarily true.

Additional Helpful Tools

While this guide primarily focuses on tasks that can be accomplished within the game engine editor, supplementary software such as image editing programs and 3D modeling tools can significantly enhance workflow. For example, image editing software like GIMP (The GIMP Development Team, 2025) enables quick adjustments to textures, such as modifying colors, contrast, or other properties. Similarly, 3D modeling tools like Blender (Blender, 2025) offer various features for optimizing and editing 3D models, capabilities that are often limited or unavailable within game engines.

Many researchers are likely familiar with image editing tools for creating figures or stimuli, but experience with 3D modeling software like Blender is often less common. This can make learning Blender alongside Unity or Unreal Engine feel overwhelming. The good news is that 3D modeling does not have to be mastered to benefit from Blender. Simple tasks, such as reducing the polygon count of a model or making small adjustments, require mainly a basic understanding of Blender's interface and its import/export process.

Throughout this guide, we will highlight opportunities to use 3D modeling and image editing software to increase flexibility and improve the optimization of models and textures. Incorporating these tools into the workflow can provide greater control and efficiency when creating high-quality, customized virtual environments. That said, it is perfectly fine to focus solely on the game engine at first and explore external tools as confidence is gained.

Note that in the article we refer to the person building the application as the 'user', and the person in the VR experiencing it as the 'participant'. So the user designs, programs and implements the application in which the participant is immersed.

Open research environments

As mentioned above, almost all kinds of assets needed to develop a virtual environment can be acquired in several online stores. While this can speed up the development process immensely, it comes with limitations regarding open science and the sharing of research materials. The licenses attached to these assets, while permitting use in research, education, and even commercial applications, usually restrict the redistribution of the raw files, such as individual models or animations. This restriction directly conflicts with the principles of open science, where the goal is to freely and transparently share research materials, including code, environments, and data. Since researchers are unable to share the entire VR project—including the assets—others cannot fully reproduce or build on the work.

Fortunately, many sources do offer high-quality assets under more permissive licenses. Websites such as [AmbientCG.com](https://www.ambientcg.com), [Polyhaven.com](https://polyhaven.com), and [Sharetextures.com](https://sharetextures.com) provide extensive libraries of textures and 3D models released under Creative Commons Zero (CC0) licenses. (*A CC0 license means the creator has waived all copyright and related rights, effectively dedicating the work to the public domain*).

However, truly open-license assets, such as those under a CC0 license, are significantly less common than their commercial counterparts, which greatly limits the range of available content and often it becomes necessary to fill gaps with purchased assets that do not have open licenses. Additionally, many CC0 3D models are designed for pre-rendered applications, such as creating images or videos, where rendering high frame rates in real-time is not required. As a result, these models frequently lack the optimization needed for real-time rendering, making it necessary to reduce polygon counts, reduce the resolution and number textures, or adjust other properties to meet the demands of VR rendering. Moreover, navigating the wide variety of licenses can be confusing or overwhelming for researchers who simply want to share VR environments without legal hurdles.

Ideally, researchers would have access to open, license-free asset libraries optimized for VR that include complete environments. Such complete environments offer a wide range of content while maintaining coherence in quality, style, and realism, making it significantly easier to create experiments with a consistent visual aesthetic compared to assembling assets from various online collections. This not only can help researchers get started with their VR experiments but also enables them to share their complete VR projects—including all assets—without legal or licensing restrictions. We are not the first to recognize the importance of open research assets, as others have already made significant contributions by publishing collections of 3D models (e.g., Peeters, 2018; Popic et al., 2020; Tromp et al., 2020). Building on this idea of open resources to support VR development and open science, we are releasing a Unity project that includes six virtual environments developed from our previous and ongoing research, all published under a creative commons licenses, mostly CC0. These environments range from a small test chamber and everyday interiors, such as an office or a living room, to a scene resembling the Roman Pantheon. The Unity project is available for download at:

<https://gitlab.com/eventlabprojects/openenvironments>

Real-Time Rendering

When learning new skills or techniques in any field, it is often helpful—and sometimes essential—to begin by understanding foundational principles, even if they may seem theoretical or less immediately engaging. Real-time rendering is no exception. To create a realistic yet well-optimized virtual environment, a basic understanding of real-time rendering and the frame rendering process is essential. In the following sections, we will provide an overview of the core concepts underlying real-time rendering before moving on to the practical steps of setting up a virtual environment. This foundational knowledge will enable better understanding of where performance bottlenecks may arise and how to identify and avoid them.

Rendering refers to the process that leads to the display of sensory data. We can think of visual rendering (computer graphics), auditory rendering, haptic rendering, and even olfactory. Mainly VR devices today deal with visual auditory rendering. *Real-time* rendering means that the frame rate of display is fast enough that real-time interaction is possible. For example, in VR as the participant is moving their head, so at least the visual and auditory displays update accordingly in a way that there are no lags or glitches that are noticeable. In computer graphics, "real-time" refers to the ability of a system to process and display images quickly enough to provide a smooth and continuous experience to the participant. This typically involves rendering frames at a rate of at least 30 frames per second (FPS) for traditional – non-VR – applications. Typically the refresh rate of the graphical display itself would be at least 60 frames a second, and the graphics rendering must be able to keep up with that – i.e., produce new frames fast enough to keep up with the hardware. Hence 'real-time' means that the VR would be an interactive environment that responds seemingly instantaneously to participant inputs, allowing them to navigate and interact with virtual worlds naturally and seamlessly.

It's important to note that the term "real-time" can be somewhat misleading. Not all aspects of a scene are computed in every frame. To optimize performance, many elements such as lighting, shadows, and reflections are often pre-calculated or "baked" into the environment. This mix of pre-computed elements and real-time processing enables the engine to simulate complex visual worlds at high frame rates.

Performance Optimization in Real-Time Rendering

Every system for real-time rendering, whether it is a high-end gaming PC or a standalone VR headset like Meta Quest or Pico Neo, has finite processing power and memory resources. Every additional computation, visual effect, higher-resolution texture, or extra object added to the scene consumes processing resources. Optimization is not just a final step but a mindset that begins with development. This does not mean being overly cautious or hesitant to add elements but rather having the awareness to make informed decisions about what will impact rendering performance. With this understanding, costly mistakes can be avoided and the scene can be confidently enhanced, knowing what additions are safe and what might require more care. For example, while polygons used to be a major concern, modern GPUs—

even in the latest generation of standalone VR systems—handle high polygon counts fairly well. In this guide, we will focus instead on other factors that are more likely to cause performance bottlenecks in contemporary VR applications.

Developing VR introduces additional challenges, as VR rendering demands significantly greater performance than standard computer screen rendering. To maintain low latency for participant comfort and prevent simulator sickness, VR applications require higher frame rates, typically ranging between 72 FPS and 120 FPS on high-resolution displays. VR also requires stereo rendering, which involves rendering the scene twice from two slightly different perspectives, one for each eye, to create the stereoscopic 3D effect, greatly increasing the rendering workload. These challenges are further exacerbated by the recent shift from high-end PC-powered VR systems to the increasing use of standalone systems with limited computational power.

When a computer fails to maintain the target frame rate, it is said to "drop frames," resulting in fewer frames being displayed per second than intended. This leads to a choppy or stuttering visual experience, disrupting the smoothness of motion.

One key concept to understand is that in real-time rendering applications that struggle to deliver new frames at the target frame rate is the difference between GPU-bound and CPU-bound. GPU-bound means that the Graphics Processing Unit (GPU)—the component responsible for rendering images and videos—is typically the limiting factor causing the performance problems. In contrast, the Central Processing Unit (CPU) manages tasks such as game logic, physics, and artificial intelligence. Knowing whether an application is CPU-bound or GPU-bound is the first step in identifying potential problems, as it allows the avoidance processes that are not handled by the limiting component.

Importantly, performance optimization is not just about making the application run; it is about ensuring it runs smoothly and reliably. Poor performance and frame drops not only break the illusion of being in a virtual environment but also serve as strong triggers for motion sickness. In research settings, this can lead to higher dropout rates from the study and also affect the behavior of participants who complete the experiment. Participants may experience symptoms that distract them from their tasks, reducing overall task performance, or they might alter their bodily movements to compensate for the lag (J. Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, since the sampling rate of behavioral data such as motion tracking data is often tied to the frame rate, frame drops can also result in data loss (Wiesing et al., 2020).

VR applications, regardless of whether designed for research or entertainment, must consistently achieve their target frame rate to ensure a smooth and comfortable experience. The ideal frame rate depends on various factors, including the hardware in use. For instance, increasing the frame rate from 72 FPS to 90 FPS requires the system to process and render roughly 20% more frames per second, which may not always be feasible, especially on lower-end systems. As a general rule, while a higher frame rate is desirable, the frame rate must be

consistently maintained. Otherwise, it is better to choose a lower, stable frame rate than to aim for a higher FPS with inconsistent performance.

To mitigate lags when the hardware cannot maintain the target frame rate, VR systems employ techniques that reuse and adjust the last rendered frame based on the participant's most recent head movements. In SteamVR, this process is known as reprojection, while on the Meta Quest, it is referred to as Asynchronous Time Warp (ATW). However, both techniques account only for rotational head movements and do not correct linear movements, which can result in noticeable lag when participants navigate through the environment.

Advanced methods such as SteamVR's Motion Smoothing and Meta Quest's Asynchronous SpaceWarp (ASW) enhance this approach by generating new "synthetic frames" instead of merely reusing previous ones. These synthetic frames account for both rotational and translational movements, thereby filling in frames when the GPU cannot sustain the target frame rate. While these techniques improve smoothness and reduce perceived lag, they can introduce visual artifacts like ghosting or distortion, particularly in scenes with rapid movement.

Therefore, while reprojecting frame and synthetic frame generation methods can help alleviate lags and improve participant comfort, they come with inherent drawbacks. The optimal strategy remains to optimize the application, so it does not drop frames and always meets the target frame rate.

That said, while performance optimization is crucial, it does not mean over-optimization is necessary. There is no reason to avoid using available resources if they can enhance the visual fidelity of the scene—something that is almost always the case. Effective optimization is not just about reducing polygons or draw calls; it is about using the available resources efficiently to achieve the best possible visual quality while ensuring smooth performance.

Finding the optimal balance between visual fidelity and rendering performance is rarely straightforward, often requiring a fair amount of experimentation and adjustment. In particular, selecting appropriate assets like 3D models and textures can be challenging. With the rendering demand of VR rendering in mind it is tempting to start directly with lower-resolution models or textures, in the interest of frame rate stability. While such conservative choices do ensure that the VR application will run smoothly, they also lead to an unnecessarily low-fidelity experience and unused potential.

If the ultimate goal is to maximize realism, it's generally best to start with higher-quality assets and then scale back as needed. Reducing polygon counts or decreasing texture resolution is usually easier than trying to enhance low-fidelity assets once they have been committed to. This does not mean that 4K textures on every surface should automatically be chosen or that only models with an extremely high polygon count should be used. Instead, be reasonable when selecting or creating assets. For example, if there barely a noticeable difference

between the 1K and 2K versions of a texture, the lower resolution texture should be preferred. Similarly, objects that will only be visible from a distance can safely use lower-resolution textures and fewer polygons. On the other hand, if a 4K texture significantly enhances the look of a key object viewed up close, then it is often worth the extra cost.

If performance problems arise once the scene is fully developed and it is suspected that texture resolution is the culprit, it is quite easy to reduce texture sizes right within Unreal or Unity. Conversely, if low-resolution textures are initially used, there is no “Enhance!” button that can magically improve them—at least not yet. With the rapid advancements in generative AI, such features may be closer than we think.

However, identifying bottlenecks—whether from texture resolution, object count, or other factors—requires knowing how to use profiling tools and interpret their outputs. A conceptual understanding of the processes involved in rendering a single frame is crucial for recognizing where performance bottlenecks arise and for effectively using profiling tools to address them.

The Game Loop

At the core of game engines is the game loop, a repeating sequence of operations the engine goes through to render a new frame. This loop consists of a series of processing steps that the engine follows in a mostly fixed order to update the game state and produce the next frame for rendering.

At the start of each iteration of the game loop, usually, the input from the participant is checked. This input might come from various devices, such as keyboards or handheld controllers, and influences what happens in the game.

Once input has been processed, the engine moves on to updating the game state. This stage involves several systems working together to establish how the virtual world has changed since the last frame. Character animations are recalculated based on time and input, physics simulations determine the movement and interaction of objects under the influence of forces and collisions, and any rule-based logic—such as whether a door should open when the participant approaches—is executed. At the same time, the spatial properties of every object in the scene, such as position, rotation, and scale, are recalculated based on these changes. Essentially, the first step in rendering a frame is to figure out how the scene has changed from the previous frame, accounting for things like movement, collisions, and animations.

After determining where everything is, the computer has to determine which objects have to be rendered. In virtual reality, the participant is surrounded by a 360-degree environment; however, at any given moment, only a portion of the entire scene is visible. To optimize performance, the game engine determines which objects fall within the participant's view after updating physics and scene dynamics. This process, known as culling, ensures that only visible elements are processed for rendering, avoiding unnecessary computations for out-of-view objects.

The first stage of culling is frustum culling. The engine calculates a viewing frustum, which is a 3D, pyramid-like shape (or cone for wide-angle lenses) that represents the area visible to the virtual camera. The apex is by the eyes of the participant (in reality the location of the head-mounted display tracking device, offset to the likely position of the eyes). The dimensions of this frustum are determined by the camera's field of view, aspect ratio, and near and far clipping planes. Any object outside this frustum is excluded from the rendering.

Beyond frustum culling, other forms of culling can be performed, such as occlusion culling. Occlusion culling ensures that objects hidden behind other objects are not rendered, such as a tree hidden behind a wall. These culling operations take place on the CPU, as they involve calculations related to the positioning and visibility of objects in the game world. There are additional culling methods that further optimize performance based on specific criteria. For example, distance culling removes objects that exceed a certain distance from the observer. These techniques, along with frustum and occlusion culling, work together to ensure that the rendering process focuses only on what truly contributes to the player's experience while minimizing computational overhead.

Once it has been determined which objects have to be rendered, the CPU sends the necessary rendering instructions (draw calls) to the GPU, which handles the actual geometry using the *graphics render pipeline*. But before we can look into the graphics rendering pipeline, we need to understand the building block of the virtual environment, the polygonal mesh.

The Polygon Mesh

A polygon mesh, often simply referred to as a "mesh," represents a 3D object and serves as the foundational element of virtual environments. A mesh is made up of vertices, edges, and faces that define the form of a three-dimensional object (Figure 1). Vertices are points in 3D space where edges meet, and edges are the line segments that connect these vertices to form the structure of a mesh. Faces within a mesh are typically polygons, which can take various shapes with three or more edges and vertices, such as quadrilaterals or other complex geometries. However, during rendering, all polygons are converted into triangles, as GPUs are optimized to process triangles—the simplest and most efficient 3D shape. This conversion is crucial for assessing a mesh's performance cost, as the relevant metric for performance is the total number of triangles, not polygons.

Figure 1. Illustration of a 3D mesh showing its structural components. The vertices (corners of the mesh) and edges (lines connecting the vertices) are annotated to help identify the basic geometric elements that make up the mesh. This representation is typical in computer graphics and modeling software, where such meshes are used to construct 3D models.

Graphics Render Pipeline

In real-time graphics rendering, most calculations—such as determining the color of a pixel—are relatively simple. However, given the high resolution of modern displays, the color must be calculated for an enormous number of pixels. For instance, the Quest 3 has a display resolution of 2064 x 2208 per eye, resulting in over 9.11 million pixels for both eyes. At a frame rate of 72 Hz, this means we need to calculate the color of more than 655 million pixels every second. CPUs, while powerful for general-purpose tasks, are not optimized for handling such highly parallel workloads. This is the reason why we have GPUs: they are specifically designed for parallel processing, utilizing shaders—small programs that operate on vertex and pixel data across thousands of cores simultaneously and efficiently manage the massive computational load required for real-time rendering.

Figure 2. Overview of the rendering pipeline in 3D graphics processing. The pipeline begins with the Vertex Shader, which manipulates individual vertices and applies scaling, rotation, and translation transformations. Next, the Geometry Shader receives this processed vertex data, allowing for the generation of new geometry from existing vertices (optional). The Shape Assembly stage then constructs geometric primitives (e.g., triangles) from the vertices. Following this, the Rasterize stage converts these geometric shapes into pixels on the screen, preparing for texturing and lighting. Lastly, the Pixel Shader (or Fragment Shader) determines the final color of each pixel by applying textures, lighting, and shading effects.

Shaders are small programs that run on the GPU and handle various stages of the rendering process. Some shaders are essential, like the vertex shader and pixel shader (often also called fragment shader), while others, such as the geometry shader, are optional and used for more specialized effects.

When the GPU starts rendering an object, it first executes the vertex shader (figure 2). The main role of the vertex shader is to transform the vertices of each object from "world space"—the 3D coordinate system where all game objects exist—into "screen space," which corresponds to the 2D coordinate system of the display's pixel grid, so the 3D scene can be accurately projected onto a 2D screen.

Vertex shader

But the vertex shader does more than just transform spaces. It can also modify the position of the vertices relative to each other, to create animations and visual effects. For animated characters like avatars, the vertex shader handles the deformation of mesh required for the animations, i.e., changing the positions of its vertices to animate movements like walking or facial expressions. Hence, when assessing the performance impact of vertices (or triangles, which are closely correlated), it is important to distinguish between static and animated objects. For animated objects, each vertex requires additional processing, making it more expensive to render compared to static objects. However, it is important to note that the vertex shader is limited to manipulating existing vertices; it cannot create new geometry.

Geometry shader

Generating new geometry becomes possible when using a geometry shader. Unlike the vertex shader, the geometry shader is optional and often not used in VR rendering due to performance impact. The geometry shader takes the output from the vertex shader and can add or remove vertices, creating new geometry or altering existing ones. This capability is

useful for the procedural generation of environments, such as generating new terrain or objects as the player moves through the world.

Tessellation shader

Another optional shader is the tessellation shader, which is particularly useful for creating highly detailed surfaces, such as landscapes. Tessellation dynamically subdivides polygons into smaller triangles, increasing detail when the viewer is closer to the surface and reducing it as the distance increases. This approach is especially beneficial in larger environments, such as those created with Unity's terrain system or Unreal Engine's landscape tools, as it allows the level of detail to adapt based on the viewer's distance, optimizing both visual quality and performance.

Shape assembly

After these stages, the shape assembly phase occurs. Here, individual vertices are grouped to form triangles which can then undergo rasterization. Before rasterization, the triangles are vector graphics, which means they are defined by mathematical equations describing their shapes and positions in space. However, the displays of HMDs are made of a discrete pixel grid.

Rasterization

To render the triangle, we need to convert the mathematical representations into pixels—a process known as rasterization. During rasterization, the GPU processes each triangle to determine which pixels are covered by the triangle. This involves calculating whether the center point of each pixel falls within the boundaries of a triangle. If it does, that pixel is marked to display part of the triangle's image. When multiple triangles overlap the same area on the screen, the GPU must perform this calculation for each triangle individually, even though only the triangle closest to the camera will ultimately be visible in that pixel.

Z-buffer

The GPU uses a z-buffer (also called depth buffer) to handle these visibility calculations efficiently. For each pixel, the z-buffer stores the depth value—the distance from the camera—of the closest triangle rendered so far. When processing a new triangle that overlaps the same pixel, the GPU compares its depth value against the stored value in the z-buffer. If the new triangle is closer to the camera, it replaces the existing ones; if it's farther away, it's discarded. This process, known as depth testing, is particularly important for mobile VR devices like the Meta Quest, which use tile-based rendering. In these systems, the z-buffer helps optimize memory usage by allowing early depth testing during the binning phase, potentially reducing the number of triangles that need to be processed during the actual rendering phase. However, the precision of the z-buffer can become an issue in VR, especially when rendering objects at vastly different distances, as the limited numerical precision of mobile GPUs can lead to z-fighting artifacts where triangles at similar depths flicker or intersect incorrectly.

This is illustrated with three overlapping triangles in Figure 3. One central pixel overlaps with all three triangles. The GPU will process this pixel three times, once for each triangle. However, only the closest triangle (the yellow one) will be rendered in that pixel in the final image. The calculations done for the other two triangles do not contribute to what is seen on the screen. This redundant processing is known as overdraw.

Figure 3. Illustration of the rasterization process, which transforms geometric data into pixel data for rendering: Each triangle in a 3D scene is projected onto a 2D grid, where the grid cells represent screen pixels. This example shows three triangles (yellow, red, and blue), for which the GPU determines the pixels they overlap. If multiple triangles overlap a pixel, the GPU rasterizes each triangle and then calculates which one is closest to the observer, discarding the others to ensure correct visibility.

Overdraw occurs when the GPU spends time processing pixels for triangles that are eventually hidden from view because they are behind other objects. This increases the rendering workload without improving the visual output. In scenes with many overlapping objects, overdraw can significantly affect performance by consuming processing power on calculations that do not affect the final rendering result. Overdraw occurs for example when dealing with translucent objects, like glass of a window. Here, the GPU must render both the object behind the window and the glass of the window itself, blending the layers to achieve transparency effects. But also opaque objects can cause overdraw, for example when foreground objects obscure parts of the objects in the background, as the GPU must rasterize all triangles, even those that are occluded by others. Depth culling helps mitigate this by discarding triangles hidden behind closer objects, reducing the amount of unnecessary pixel processing. Similarly, usually back-face culling is used to discard triangles facing away from the camera, further reducing the number of triangles the GPU must handle.

An alternative to rasterization is real-time ray tracing. Real-time ray tracing works by casting rays from the camera (or viewer's perspective) into the scene to determine how they interact with objects and light sources. Although real-time ray tracing offers impressive visual capabilities, it is currently not practical for VR rendering—especially on standalone systems—so it is outside the scope of this . Similarly, rendering techniques such as Light Field rendering (Mortensen et al., 2007) or Gaussian Splatting (Kerbl et al., 2023) will not be discussed in this paper.

Pixel shader (fragment shader)

Importantly, the colors in Figure 3 are for illustrative purposes, as the actual color of each pixel is determined after rasterization by the pixel shader (also called fragment shader). The pixel shader computes surface effects such as diffuse and specular lighting, bump mapping, and shadows to create the final appearance of the pixels. In modern applications, the performance impact of pixel shaders is often greater than that of vertex shaders, as high-resolution textures and advanced shading techniques can greatly increase the workload for pixel processing.

In summary, the graphics render pipeline progresses through stages that first process the geometry at the vertex level (world-to-screen space transformation and deformation), then at the triangle level (shape assembly and rasterization), and finally at the pixel level (colors).

Draw Calls

Draw calls are commands issued by the CPU to the GPU instructing it to render objects on the screen. Each draw call communicates the details of what and how to render or draw an object to produce the final visual output. To prepare for a draw call, the CPU sets up resources and changes internal settings on the GPU. These settings are collectively called the render state. Changes to the render state, such as switching to a different material, are the most resource-intensive operations the graphics API performs. The time-consuming part is not the communication itself, but the need for the CPU to manage these changes for each draw call. The more draw calls there are, the more the CPU has to switch between different states and prepare instructions, which quickly can become a performance bottleneck. By reducing the number of draw calls through techniques like batching or combining objects (described in more detail later), it is possible to lower the number of draw calls.

A common misunderstanding is that one object to render means one draw call. A single object can result in several draw calls when it contains more than one material. A material defines how the surface of an object looks, including its color, texture, and reflectivity (also explained in more detail later). An object can have multiple materials applied to different parts of it, like having one material for the glass of a window and another for the frame. In this case, the engine divides the mesh into sub-meshes, one containing the part with the glass material and the other one with the material of the frame and processes the mesh as if it were two meshes, resulting in two draw calls.

Also, when the object casts shadows in real time it results in further draw calls.

Additionally, in VR we need to render the scene twice, once for the left and once for the right eye, from slightly different angles. As a result, objects visible to both eyes would result in twice as many draw calls compared to rendering only for one eye. The typical way to account for this is by employing techniques like single-pass stereo or multiview rendering. These techniques optimize the rendering process by allowing the GPU to render the scene once and then adjust the image for each eye. This is achieved by applying slight modifications to the perspective of the rendered image to match the viewpoints of both eyes.

Rendering Pass

A rendering pass is a single stage in the process of creating the final image seen on the screen. During each pass, the computer processes specific information, such as geometry, lighting, or shading, and writes the results into a texture. Some scenes require multiple passes to add details like shadows, reflections, or special effects, with each pass focusing on a different aspect of the image. Each pass contributes to the overall number of draw calls, as objects may need to be processed multiple times across different passes. Think of it like painting a picture in layers, where each layer adds something new, such as colors, highlights, or textures. Combining these passes results in the complete, visually rich image seen in a game or virtual experience.

Tile-based renderers

Unlike desktop GPUs, which can consume a lot of power and have access to large amounts of memory, mobile GPUs—such as those used in standalone HMDs—operate under strict power constraints and highly limited memory. To address these limitations, mobile GPUs employ a technique called tiled rendering, which involves dividing the image into smaller pieces, or tiles, and processing each tile individually. So instead of rendering the entire frame at once, the frame is rendered in small pieces, to account for the limited memory.

Before rendering, mobile GPUs perform a binning process to determine how triangles map onto the tiled grid. During this phase, the vertex shader calculate the positions of vertices and identify which tiles the resulting triangles will affect, optimizing subsequent rendering steps. Each triangle is associated with specific tiles based on its vertex positions. This selective association ensures that during the rendering phase, the GPU executes pixel shaders only for the triangles relevant to each tile.

The vertex shader plays a crucial role but is also a point of resource contention. Each triangle's vertex shader might be executed multiple times—once during the binning process to determine tile coverage, and again during the actual rendering phase for each tile the triangle overlaps with. While this repeated execution is necessary for maintaining memory efficiency, it increases the computational load.

Hence, when operating on a system with a tile-based rendering architecture, techniques that require extensive memory access or are computationally expensive on the vertex shader can have a greater performance impact on the GPU compared to desktop GPUs.

Rendering Settings

When starting a new VR project, the first step is to properly configure the game engine. This involves reviewing the recommended and required settings for engines like Unreal or Unity, as outlined by HMD manufacturers such as Meta or Pico. For example, if the application is intended to run on standalone headsets like the Meta Quest or Pico, installation of the appropriate Android packages will be needed, such as the Oculus Integration or Pico SDK. For PC-based VR systems like the Valve Index or HTC Vive, SteamVR or OpenXR plugins are required. Fortunately, detailed setup information for various engine and hardware combinations is readily available online and can be easily found using search engines.

Correctly setting up rendering settings is crucial not only for hardware compatibility but also because it can often affect the visual appearance of the scene. For instance, the Meta Quest 3 in standalone mode requires switching Unity's default gamma color space to linear, which directly impacts how colors are rendered. If the colors of the surfaces in the scene are defined before changing the color space, their appearance may change afterward, potentially requiring fine-tuning to achieve the intended look.

Similarly, the required or recommended texture encoding format often varies depending on the target platform and should be set correctly at the begin of the development. If the correct format is applied after importing or generating numerous textures, the game engine must re-encode all assets. This re-encoding process can frequently take 30 minutes or more, depending on hardware performance and project complexity. During this time, the engine may become unresponsive, thereby disrupting the workflow.

Similar disruptions occur when changing the project's target platform, such as from Windows to Android, due to the necessary recompilation of shaders and platform-specific assets. This quickly happens when developing an application intended for standalone Android-based HMDs (e.g., Meta Quest or Pico Neo) while using a Windows-based PC development environment with tools like Quest Link. Although recompilation time itself may not represent a critical concern, it tends to occur at inconvenient moments and can be easily avoided by starting with the correct setting in the first place.

Choosing the render pipeline

Unity provides three different scriptable rendering pipelines tailored to different needs and hardware capabilities. These are the Built-in Render Pipeline, the Universal Render Pipeline (URP), and the High-Definition Render Pipeline (HDRP).

Think of them as different tools for painting a picture: the Built-in Render Pipeline is like using a basic set of brushes—it gets the job done but lacks the finesse and efficiency for modern applications. The HDRP, on the other hand, is like using an advanced digital painting toolkit; it's designed for high-end hardware, delivering cutting-edge graphics with detailed lighting and shading, perfect for projects that work in high-end hardware aiming for visual fidelity.

Meanwhile, the URP serves as a middle ground, like a versatile set of brushes that balance quality and performance, making it ideal for VR projects where performance is critical.

Unreal Engine handles rendering differently from Unity, using a unified system with configurable features rather than distinct pipelines. Developers can enable or disable advanced options like ray tracing or Lumen to suit hardware and performance needs. Unlike Unity, where a render pipeline must be chosen at the start and requires some work to switch the rendering pipeline at a later point, Unreal offers flexibility within a single framework, though careful configuration is needed to balance performance and visual quality.

In the Open Environments project, we use the Universal Render Pipeline and generally recommend that readers work with URP when developing VR experiences in Unity because it provides the necessary performance for VR while maintaining good visual quality. Another advantage of both the URP and HDRP over the Built-in Render Pipeline is their support for Shader Graph, a visual scripting tool to easily create custom shaders—a topic we will explore in more detail later.

When setting up a new URP project in Unity using the URP template, Unity offers three fidelity profiles with recommended rendering settings for both high-end and low-end platforms. By default, the “High Fidelity” profile is selected, and it is generally advisable to stick with it. However, it comes with Screen Space Ambient Occlusion enabled in the “URP-HighFidelity-Renderer”, which should be removed due to its high-performance cost.

Forward vs Deferred Rendering

In real-time rendering, forward rendering and deferred rendering are two different approaches to how lighting and shading are calculated.

Deferred rendering decouples geometry and lighting calculations by first rendering the scene into multiple textures that store geometric information, such as position, color, and normals. This information is then used in a second render pass to apply lighting and shading effects, allowing for efficient handling of multiple light sources. While deferred rendering can handle complex lighting with many real-time lights efficiently, it typically requires substantial memory and advanced graphics hardware, which can be a limitation for low-end platforms. Forward rendering applies lighting and shading calculations directly as objects are drawn, requiring fewer intermediate buffers and less memory usage. Furthermore, in contrast to deferred rendering, it also supports Multisample Anti-Aliasing (MSAA), which is the standard anti-aliasing for VR applications (see part about anti-aliasing). However, forward rendering is less efficient and has a greater performance impact when rendering scenes with many real-time light sources, as it must calculate the effects of each light individually for every object.

In summary, forward rendering is the preferred choice for VR due to its better performance and support for MSAA, which is crucial for reducing visual artifacts in the highly dynamic, immersive VR environment.

Anti Aliasing

Figure 4. Illustration of aliasing versus anti-aliasing. The upper left shows the pixel grid and the upper right a disc to be rendered on this pixel grid. The lower left shows the rendered disc without anti-aliasing, showing jagged edges. On the right, the jagged edges are smoothed out using anti-aliasing.

Aliasing in rendering occurs when the pixel grid used to display an image is not fine enough to capture the smooth transitions of geometry, leading to visual artifacts like jagged edges (Figure. 4) This happens because a single pixel may oversimplify complex details, causing sharp changes in color or intensity between adjacent pixels that do not reflect the true geometry of the scene. The core issue is that the rasterization process converts continuous geometric information into discrete pixel data, and this sampling can miss important visual information, especially along polygon edges or fine details.

Aliasing becomes especially noticeable when the camera is in motion. In VR, the virtual camera moves with the participant's head movements, and since the head is always in subtle motion—even when the participant tries to remain still—aliasing artifacts are amplified. This makes anti-aliasing essential for VR rendering, despite its performance cost. Multisample Anti-Aliasing (MSAA) is particularly recommended for VR over methods like Temporal Anti-Aliasing (TAA) or Super Sampling Anti-Aliasing (SSAA)

TAA smooths edges by blending data from previous frames, making it computationally efficient and effective for a variety of aliasing issues. However, can introduce blurring and ghosting artifacts, which are particularly noticeable during head movements in VR.

Better results can in VR be achieved with SSAA, which renders the scene at a higher resolution before downsampling to the display resolution. During downsampling color values of neighboring pixel values are averaged, producing smoother edges and reducing aliasing. However, SSAA is highly performance-intensive, making it impractical when rendering on a low-end system.

A better alternative is MSAA, which smooths edges by sampling multiple points within each pixel to determine geometry coverage. Unlike SSAA, which performs a full shading calculation

for each sample, MSAA performs a single shading calculation for all samples altogether, which is then used to determine the final color of the pixel.

For most VR projects, MSAA should always be set to 4x, meaning four samples are taken for each pixel, which provides a good balance between performance and visual quality, ensuring smooth edges without excessive resource demands.

Single and multi-pass rendering

Multi-pass and single-pass rendering are two methodologies employed to handle scene processing in 3D environments, such as virtual reality (VR), each with distinct impacts on system performance and graphical fidelity.

Multi-pass rendering processes the scene separately for each eye, greatly increasing the workload significantly on the CPU and to a smaller but still relevant degree on the GPU. Single-pass rendering renders the image for only once and then projects both right-eye and left-eye views of the geometry. However, this introduces limitations that can affect some shading or post-processing effects. Effects that rely heavily on screen-space calculations—such as screen-space reflections—may not render correctly because they depend on depth information that is unique to each eye's perspective. Furthermore, concerns have been raised that single-pass rendering can produce incorrect images on HMDs with asymmetric projections (i.e., the displays are slightly tilted for each eye to better match human vision and improve rendering efficiency), potentially causing visual discomfort and depth perception issues. The latter might be especially relevant to research concerned about e.g., spatial perception (Kapouranis, 2020). To address these issues, modern approaches use techniques like multiview rendering, which allows each eye's view to be rendered with its projection parameters within a single pass, improving both performance and visual accuracy.

Ultimately, the decision between single-pass and multi-pass stereo rendering depends on the VR project's specific requirements and the CPU's and to a lesser degree the GPU's workload. If the application is running without performance problems using multi-pass stereo rendering, switching to single-pass will not provide any performance gains.

Getting Started

Before beginning the development of a virtual environment, there should be a plan of exactly what is expected to be displayed and what interactions will be possible. While it is easy to describe an environment and an interaction, of course in VR every single aspect of the final output and possibility of interaction must have been programmed. Virtual environments are not merely backdrops; they are part of the stimuli in the planned experimental study that can significantly influence participants' behavior and responses. For instance, a social interaction experiment might require a suitable and believable setting, such as a café or an office, whereas having the interaction on the edge of the rooftop of a skyscraper might be less suitable. On the other hand, a study investigating the fear of heights would probably benefit from taking place on the roof of a high skyscraper.

The design of the environment also directly impacts how participants perceive and interact with the virtual world. Poor lighting could obscure relevant visual details such as facial expressions, thus reducing the clarity of social cues or an overly dark environment might create discomfort. Similarly, environmental features such as height or spatial constraints can evoke specific emotions or reactions, like unease or distraction.

Well designed virtual environments can also guide attention, subtly directing participants toward key elements of the study. Additionally, the mood conveyed by the environment—whether calming, neutral, or anxiety-inducing—can influence participants' emotional states and potentially affect experimental outcomes. By recognizing these factors during the planning phase, researchers can create virtual environments that not only serve their purpose but also enhance the reliability and validity of their findings.

It is often assumed that creating a realistic rendering is more challenging than designing for example a low-poly environment. However, a stylized rendered environment, such as a low-poly environment, involves more than simply using fewer polygons; it requires a cohesive and carefully crafted art style. While photorealistic rendering is technically demanding, its artistic direction is straightforward—replicate what exists in the real world. In contrast, stylized rendering requires the development and consistent application of a unique visual style across all objects in the scene.

Take advantage of the fact that we are surrounded by countless real-world environments. When starting to develop a virtual setting, begin by finding a real-world example—whether it is an actual place or simply a photograph—that aligns with the idea being pursued. However, using a reference does not mean that every detail must be exactly replicated. The focus is more on capturing the essential aspects: overall proportions and shape of a room, how objects like furniture are arranged, how light hits surfaces, and the distribution of shadows and reflections. References can also provide a guide for subtle details like surface imperfections or the irregularities of everyday objects. Getting these seemingly small details right can make a huge difference in achieving realism.

Creating a new environment

In the following, we will outline the process of creating a virtual environment which can be broadly divided into three main steps: setting up the geometry, shading, and lighting. Geometry involves arranging 3D meshes to construct the scenery. Shading defines how the surfaces of these meshes respond to light, determining properties such as color, texture, and glossiness. Lighting involves adding light sources to the scene to illuminate it and create effects like shadows and reflections.

While these steps are conceptually distinct, in practice, they are deeply interconnected. However, breaking the process into these steps is a useful way to explain the different aspects of rendering, even if they overlap significantly in practice.

Setting up the geometry

When designing virtual environments, particularly from scratch, it is easy to misjudge the scale of objects and spaces. A common pitfall is unintentionally creating disproportionately large environments, which can make rooms or areas feel unnaturally spacious and unrealistic. Furthermore, larger environments require more objects and details to make them feel realistic, which not only increases the time and effort needed for design but also unnecessarily increases the rendering workload.

To avoid this, one way is to base the environment on real-world measurements, such as measuring the dimensions of a real room and furniture in it or looking up typical dimensions online. However, a more intuitive approach is to simply start by placing familiar objects of known size in the scene. For example, in Figure 5, the left image shows an empty plane, which provides no sense of scale. The right image, however, includes two sofas and a coffee table, making it immediately clear that the plane would be excessively large if it were supposed to become e.g., a typical living room. Using one or two reference objects of familiar size gives an intuitive idea of the scale of the scene. Here it doesn't matter if the objects will be part of the final environment or will just serve as a temporary size reference, as long as it is scaled correctly.

As a general rule, create environments no larger than necessary, as larger spaces require more assets to fill the scene with life.

Figure 5. Screenshots of two scenes, on the left the scene consists of a single plane, making it impossible to estimate the size of the plane. On the right, two sofas, a coffee table, and a carpet have been added to the plane. Since the furniture is scaled in typical dimensions of their real-world counterparts, we get immediately as sense of the scale and that the place shown in the screenshots would be too big if the goal is to render a typical living room.

When laying out the scene, whether it is a single interior room or an outdoor environment, an important aspect to enhance realism is asymmetry and irregularities. While this might be obvious for natural outdoor environments, artificial interiors, such as a typical living room, are often not perfectly symmetrical. Real-world architectural spaces often feature unique irregularities, like a narrower section of a room, or a protruding wall to accommodate infrastructure such as a chimney, or a bay window. Including these irregularities in the virtual environment can greatly enhance the sense of authenticity and make the space more visually interesting compared to perfectly square or rectangular rooms.

Furthermore, the real world, even in seemingly tidy and clean environments, is full of small irregularities and imperfections. These imperfections are everywhere—the slightly crooked angle of a painting on the wall, a scuffed floorboard, or the way cushions on a sofa are never perfectly aligned. Similarly, books on a shelf often exhibit slight chaos, with some sticking out, leaning, or tilted at different angles. A cabinet with movable drawers might have one left slightly open.

Incorporating such details into a virtual environment can make it feel more authentic and relatable. Sterile, overly perfect spaces, on the other hand, often feel lifeless and artificial, like staged advertisements for luxury apartments or designer products.

Adding personal traces—objects that suggest someone was just there—takes this realism even further. A coffee cup with a ring of liquid at the base, an empty plate with crumbs or a cake fork, an open book with pages mid-turn, or a remote control casually left on the couch. Clothes draped over a chair, a pair of shoes left by the door, or a jacket slung on the back of the sofa. In a bedroom, a sock might lie forgotten on the floor, or a bedside table might have a half-empty water glass, candy wrappers, or a phone charging. Even subtle touches, like a magazine opened to a random page or a scattered set of keys on the kitchen counter. These small imperfections and personal traces subtly suggest that the environment has a history and has been actively used, making it feel alive rather than staged and sterile.

To prepare the scene for lighting, include lamp models or other visible light sources as part of the design. These objects will serve as the basis for the scene's illumination, we will discuss later. A reference image of a similar real-world room can be invaluable for selecting appropriate lamps and arrangement them. Typical indoor spaces often feature multiple light sources; for instance, a bedroom might include a ceiling light, a bedside lamp, and a desk lamp. Using multiple light sources can not only enhance realism but can also used to create focal points in the environment. For example, a bright lamp on a desk in an otherwise dimly lit room can be used to draw the participant's attention to the desk.

The realism of the lighting can be further enhanced by combining interior lights with sunlight. For this reason, interior spaces should ideally include at least one window to allow light from the outside to enter the room.

Geometry and performance

When evaluating the performance impact of the designed models, the focus is primarily on the number of vertices, triangles, and objects in the scene. While earlier GPUs were limited by low triangle counts, modern GPUs—including those in the latest generation of standalone VR headsets like the Meta Quest 3—are capable of handling rather high numbers. For example, the Quest 3 can process up to 1.3–1.8 million triangles, though many interior environments require far fewer. In Figure 6, the scene uses approximately 49,000 triangles, which represents only a small fraction of the system's capabilities, leaving ample room to add more detail without performance concerns. It is also worth noting that the recommended upper triangle limit refers to what the system can render simultaneously, but in practice, not all triangles in a scene are rendered at once, as typically culling is used to remove all objects outside of view from the rendering.

Hence, the triangle count is often not a limiting factor on modern GPUs unless objects are designed with an excessively high number of triangles. Developers do not need to be overly cautious or hesitant to populate a scene with objects that have a somewhat higher polygon number.

However, this does not mean that the number of triangles is unimportant. While meshes for realistic rendering should not be reduced to the point where they lose their realistic shape, they ideally also do not contain more triangles than necessary.

Reducing triangle counts can be achieved using modeling software like Blender, which offers various optimization tools, or within game engines. Unreal Engine includes built-in reduction tools, while Unity relies on third-party packages such as UModelerX. These tools typically allow the specification of the percentage of triangles to retain; for example, setting a value of 70 results in a mesh that retains 70% of the original triangle count. This enables quick experimentation with different levels of reduction and provide immediate visual feedback on how the reduction affects the model's shape. However, reducing too many triangles can cause the mesh to lose its original form, introducing clear distortions of the surfaces. The goal is to find the point where the triangle count is minimized just before noticeable distortions of the surface occur.

How well a model can be simplified with automated reduction tools without causing distortion depends a lot on the mesh's topology—the arrangement and structure of vertices, edges, and faces that make up the model. Models with intricate details or poorly designed, irregular topologies are more prone to visible deformations and surface artifacts during optimization. However, reduction tools have their limitations, and some models cannot be effectively optimized to a reasonable triangle count without introducing distortions. In such cases, manual optimization may be necessary, which requires some modeling expertise and is significantly more time-consuming than automated reduction tools. Alternatively, it is often easier to search for a better-optimized version of the same kind of object rather than investing too much effort in optimizing a specific high-poly model where automatic reduction tools fall short.

Interestingly, objects with high triangle counts are often not the ones that might be expected. For instance, the white cabinet with two glass doors on the right in Figure 6 has a total of 1,474 triangles. However, the cabinet's walls, drawers, and doors account for only 194 triangles, while the remaining 1,280 triangles are used entirely for the eight spherical knobs on the doors and drawers. Small objects with curved or irregular shapes, like these knobs, often require disproportionately more polygons to represent the shape accurately, even though these elements are minor details compared to the larger, simpler surfaces of the main object.

Figure 6. The entire scene, including objects not visible in this render, is composed of about 49K triangles

Culling

Apart from the number of triangles in each mesh, one crucial way to optimize the scene is to render only the necessary objects. While this generally means rendering only what the participant can see, in large environments it can also mean rendering only what contributes

to the scene. For example, a football 500 meters away would have little impact on the scene, as it would be too distant to be visible. Therefore, it is important to exclude the football, even if it is technically within the participant's line of sight.

As previously explained, by default, game engines use frustum culling, which excludes objects outside the frustum, typically corresponding to the field of view. This is usually sufficient for smaller environments, like a single interior, where nothing exists beyond the visible area. However, in more complex environments, such as those with multiple adjacent rooms or large outdoor areas, frustum culling alone is not optimal because it does not account for occlusion. Occlusion Culling works by determining whether objects are hidden behind other objects from the viewpoint of the camera. The engine calculates what is visible from the observer's perspective, often using depth maps or other techniques to identify which objects are occluded by others.

In large-scale environments, distance-based culling is often used to optimize performance by excluding objects that are far from the observer from rendering, based on their size and distance. For example, objects the size of a car or smaller might be culled when they are more than 500 meters away, while larger objects, such as buildings, would remain visible. This approach reduces the number of objects processed without significantly affecting the overall appearance of the scene.

Level of Detail (LOD)

In Unity, distance culling can be implemented by Level of Detail (LOD) groups, refers to a technique to reduce the complexity of distant objects in a scene. An LOD group consists of multiple versions of the same mesh with decreasing polygon counts (and possibly reduced texture sizes or simpler shaders models). This allows the engine to swap out higher-detail models with simpler, lower-detail models as the object moves further from the camera. In Unity, LOD groups are often used for distance culling, with multiple levels of meshes defined for objects: LOD0 for high-detail meshes, LOD1 for medium detail, and LOD2 for low-detail meshes and so forth. Beyond a certain distance, typically LOD3, the mesh is culled out.

Skybox

In most virtual environments, the explorable area is limited to where participants can move, but the visible space often extends far beyond these navigable boundaries. For instance, in environments with windows or outdoor settings, participants can see distant areas they cannot directly explore. Leaving these regions empty can break immersion, making the virtual world appear to abruptly end in a void. To maintain a sense of realism, it is important to fill these visible but unreachable outdoor areas with content to create the illusion of a world that extends beyond what the participant can see. Fortunately, this can often be achieved relatively easily and with minimal performance impact using a bit of extra geometry and a well-designed skybox.

A skybox is a texture or procedurally generated image projected onto a sphere. It is always rendered first, before any other geometry, ensuring that it remains in the background and

cannot be reached, no matter how far the participant moves. In Unity, new scenes include a default procedural skybox that simulates atmospheric effects, such as a sun whose position and color change dynamically based on the rotation of the scene's directional light—typically used to simulate sunlight or moonlight (Figure 7 A).

While the default skybox provides a general atmospheric backdrop, replacing it with a custom texture can significantly enhance realism. For instance, (Figure 7 B) shows the same studio scene enhanced with a 360-degree panoramic image of Barcelona as a skybox. Additionally, a balcony with a wooden fence and a few tables, and chairs were added to create a natural transition between the virtual world and the distant backdrop.

High-resolution high dynamic range images (HDRI) are commonly used as skybox textures. Free collections of these images can be found on platforms like Polyhaven.com.

When selecting a texture for a skybox, avoid images depicting objects that appear close to the observer. The skybox is always rendered at a fixed distance from the participant, regardless of movement. This creates a perceptual issue: objects on the skybox do not change in retinal size (i.e., the area of the retina stimulated by the object), whereas the retinal size of three-dimensional geometry in the scene changes with movement. Normally, as we move closer to or farther from objects, the retinal size changes accordingly, but the objects themselves are perceived as remaining the same size—a phenomenon known as “size constancy” (Weidner et al., 2014). Distance between the observer and the object is an important cue for inferring size despite variations in retinal size, but this cue is absent for the fixed-distance skybox.

As a result, objects on the skybox texture do not change in retinal size, unlike the three-dimensional geometry in the scene, creating the illusion that objects on the skybox scale up as we move closer and scale down as we move away. This effect is particularly noticeable for objects that seem close in the skybox image, but it typically is not noticeable when using HDRIs that depict distant scenes, such as landscapes or city views from tall buildings without nearby structures.

When selecting the resolution of an HDRI, it's important to remember that it represents a 360-degree spherical image— of which only a small portion is visible within the field of view at any given time. To avoid blurriness, high-resolution HDRIs of at least 4K are recommended.

Figure 7. Rendering of a TV Studio scene in two conditions. The upper rendering shows Unity's default procedural sky. In the lower rendering the sky is replaced by an HDRI showing the view over Barcelona as well as the Studio was extended by a balcony with a fence and some tables and chairs to create a natural transition between the 3D environment and the background image.

Shading

So far, we have set up the geometry of the scene, but this alone does not contain information about the surface colors or other surface properties. Although it is technically possible to store color information directly in the vertices of a mesh using vertex colors, this approach has significant limitations. For instance, attributes like reflectivity, smoothness, or texture details cannot be defined this way because they require more complex data than what can be stored in the model itself. Additionally, storing such information directly in the geometry would make the model less flexible and harder to reuse in different contexts, as changes to the surface properties would require editing the model itself.

Instead, surface properties, such as color, texture, reflectivity, and smoothness, are defined using materials. Materials often include what are commonly referred to as shaders, which are sets of instructions for the pixel shader or vertex shader that define how the surface interacts with light and how it is rendered. However, different software engines might use the terms "material" and "shader" differently, which can be a bit confusing.

In Unity, a *shader* acts like a template or recipe. It defines how surfaces can look but requires specific details to be complete. Think of it as a function with variables that need values—like color, smoothness, or metallic shine. To use this shader, create a *material* where to fill in these variables with actual values or textures. This means multiple materials can be created from the same shader, each with a different appearance.

In Unreal Engine, the process is similar in principle but starts differently. Instead of creating a shader, first begin by creating a material, which serves as both the template and the applied surface definition. This material can be modified directly to control its properties, much like Unity's shaders. However, it is common practice in Unreal to create material instances from the base material. Material instances act as copies of the original material, allowing the adjustment of specific settings—such as colors or texture maps—without altering the base material itself. This provides flexibility and efficiency, especially when reusing materials across multiple objects with slight variations.

Even if multiple versions of a material are not needed, it is advisable to use material instances in Unreal. Changing values directly in the material in Unreal requires recompiling the material, which can take seconds to minutes depending on its complexity and the hardware. This can slow down the progress, especially when experimenting with settings or textures. Material instances avoid this issue by allowing the adjustment of predefined parameters without altering the underlying shader code, eliminating the need for recompilation the entire material repeatedly.

In the following, this guide will focus on the Unity terminology, i.e., a surface shader is the template for the material and a material is the shader with all variables defined and what is applied to the surface of an object. But this is purely for convenience and the principles described below are the same for both engines, if not stated otherwise.

Physically Based Rendering

Realistic rendering relies on Physically Based Rendering (PBR), a technique that simulates how light interacts with materials based on real-world physics. Unlike traditional approaches that

rely on arbitrary values to mimic appearance, PBR uses material properties such as color, smoothness, metallicity, or translucency to define how surfaces absorb, scatter, or reflect light. For example, metals reflect most incoming light and have colored reflections based on their material, while non-metals reflect only a small, colorless portion of light and instead absorb and scatter light internally, creating their characteristic diffuse appearance. Similarly, smoothness controls how scattered or focused reflections appear. A smooth surface creates sharp, mirror-like reflections, while a rough surface (low smoothness) diffuses reflections into a broader pattern.

PBR shaders incorporate energy conservation, ensuring that surfaces never reflect more light than they receive—a common issue in older rendering systems. This inherent constraint allows artists to create materials that look correct under any lighting conditions without requiring constant manual adjustments. When lighting changes in a scene, PBR materials respond automatically in physically accurate ways, maintaining their realistic appearance and behavior.

Additionally, PBR is a standardized framework and different engines define material properties based on the same physical principles, ensuring textures and materials are interoperable across different rendering engines. This standardization allows the same textures to be used across engines while delivering consistent visual results.

Using standard shaders

Unity offers a range of built-in shaders for creating materials, from simple, optimized shaders to high-fidelity options. These shaders address a variety of common use cases, including foliage, skyboxes, and mobile platforms, offering flexibility and convenience. A key advantage of Unity's approach is its participant-friendly design: shaders can be easily selected and switched via a dropdown menu, often eliminating the need for custom shader creation.

The Standard Lit Shader (Figure 8 G) is a highly versatile PBR shader model designed for general-purpose use, making it the default choice for most applications. Its flexibility allows it to handle a wide range of surface appearances, making it suitable for many scenarios. For instance, by default, a material begins as a neutral white surface (A). Adjusting the "Base Map" color to red changes it to resemble red plastic, while increasing the Metallic value to 1 (C) creates a matte metallic look. Setting the Smoothness to 1 (D) produces a highly reflective finish, ideal for objects like shiny Christmas ornaments. Additionally, the Emission setting can make the surface glow (E), adding vibrancy or simulating light-emitting objects.

While the Standard Lit Shader is a good and performant choice for most purposes, its computational demands can become costly on lower-end hardware, particularly on older standalone systems like the Meta Quest 2. However, for objects that require realistic surface details, such as smoothness, reflectivity, or metallic effects, it remains the go-to shader due to its balance of visual quality and versatility. Careful optimization and selective use of the shader can help maintain performance on less powerful systems.

Figure 8. Illustration of different shading effects of Unity's standard lit shader (G). (A) show the default setting with a plain white surface. (B) show the same shader setting but change the color to red (using the color panel next to "base map"). In (C) the shader is additionally set to metallic. In (D) the smoothness was changed to a value of 1, making the surface completely smooth. In (E) the shader is set to emissive, making it slightly glowing. In (F) the shader was changed from opaque to transparent, making the sphere translucent.

Metallic vs Specular Workflow

Unity's Standard Shader offers two workflows for creating materials: Metallic and Specular. These workflows differ in how they define the reflection color of a surface. In the Metallic workflow, metallic materials reflect colored light based on the Base Color, while non-metallic materials reflect neutral (white) light, with the Base Color determining the diffuse appearance. In contrast, the Specular workflow provides direct control over the reflection color via a Specular value or map, offering more flexibility for both metallic and non-metallic surfaces. However, this added flexibility comes at the cost of physical accuracy, as the Specular workflow can break energy conservation principles by allowing surfaces to reflect more light than they receive. This makes the Specular workflow more suitable for stylized rendering, while the Metallic workflow is generally recommended for realistic scenes when using Unity's Standard Lit Shader.

Transparency

Switching the Surface Type from Opaque to Transparent allows materials to become translucent, enabling effects like glass or frosted surfaces (Figure 8 F). However, unlike opaque materials, transparent objects require the GPU to process multiple layers of overlapping geometry. To determine the final color of a pixel, the GPU must blend the color values of the transparent surface with those of the objects behind it. This means the same pixel is processed multiple times, resulting in overdraw. While a few small transparent objects generally have minimal impact on performance, viewing a complex scene through one or even more transparent objects, like windows with an expensive glass material, can quickly cause a noticeable performance drop.

In mixed reality using passthrough cameras such as with Meta Quest 3, transparency can be problematic because rendering pipelines must blend the virtual scene with the real-world video feed. Transparency relies on accurate sorting of objects and proper alpha blending, which determine how overlapping transparent surfaces combine visually. In mixed reality, transparency becomes more complex because the rendering engine must blend transparent virtual objects not only with other virtual elements but also with the real-world video feed, often leading to depth and sorting issues. This can cause issues like semi-transparent objects or other artifacts, because the renderer struggles to resolve the depth and layering of virtual transparent objects against the passthrough background.

Another way to create transparency is alpha clipping. However, in contrast to alpha blending, alpha clipping uses a threshold to determine whether a fragment is either fully visible or discarded. Generally, alpha clipping is cheaper than alpha blending in terms of performance, but it is an all-or-nothing effect, making it unsuitable for rendering partially translucent objects or creating effects like reflections on glass. Instead, alpha clipping is typically used for e.g., rendering foliage, where the mesh is often coarse and roughly approximates the shape of the plant. The texture's alpha channel or a dedicated opacity mask is then used to "cut out" detailed shapes, such as leaves or branches, to create a visually convincing plant while minimizing the number of triangles needed.

One- and Two-Sided shading

To reduce GPU workload, real-time rendering typically displays only the outward-facing surfaces of a mesh—a technique known as backface culling. The inward-facing sides are not rendered, making them invisible from inside the object. For example, if a participant moves their head inside a rendered cube, its faces will appear transparent from the inside. In certain cases, such as clothing, paper, or foliage, rendering both sides of a mesh is necessary. However, enabling two-sided shading increases the rendering load, as both sides of each surface must be processed and drawn.

Texture maps

In the example materials created above using the default Lit Shader, we defined surface properties—such as color, smoothness, and metallic values—uniformly across the entire

object. While this approach can produce a variety of materials, the surfaces lack textures, fine details, and the irregularities that make real-world objects look authentic. Examining the surfaces of the furniture or objects around there will hardly be a perfectly clean, flawless surface like the examples shown. In reality, most surfaces feature some kind of texture or pattern, along with imperfections like scratches, dirt, or fingerprints. These subtle details contribute to the realism of an object.

We use texture maps (or simply "maps") in PBR to achieve realistic surfaces with details and imperfections. Maps are digital images applied to the surface of a 3D model to define its appearance, color, or other surface details like bumps or reflections. They allow different parts of a surface to have varying properties. For instance, instead of applying a uniform color, we can introduce patterns, variations, or irregularities to make the surface more lifelike.

UV Maps

How can we control which part of a texture is applied to specific parts of a 3D mesh? This is achieved through UV maps. A UV map is a 2D representation of a 3D model's surface, much like unwrapping a cardboard box into a flat sheet to paint on it.

The term "UV" refers to the 2D coordinates used in the mapping process, with U and V representing the horizontal and vertical axes, respectively (since X, Y, and Z are reserved for 3D space coordinates). While this process is often described as "wrapping" the texture around the surface, it doesn't mean the texture must be wrapped in a single, continuous piece. Instead, UV mapping is more like cutting the texture into pieces and sticking those pieces onto the corresponding parts of the object.

The UV space is defined with the horizontal axis as U and the vertical axis as V, both ranging from 0 to 1 (Figure 9A). In Figure 9, the top panel shows six squares arranged in the shape of a "T". Each square corresponds to one face of the cube on the right. When a texture with colored squares matching the UV layout is applied, the cube's faces display the colors of the texture overlapping with their respective "UV islands" (Figure 9B).

Not all UV maps need to be unwrapped with each face having its own dedicated space. Instead, UV islands can overlap or be disconnected entirely. For example, in a video game, overlapping UV islands are often used to save texture space. If we move the UV island of the red face to overlap different parts of the texture, the cube's face could display four distinct colors instead of a single one (Figure 9C).

Figure 9. Illustration of UV maps. In (A) a gray cube is shown with its unwrapped UV map on the left. Each of the squares or UV islands represents one side of the cube. In (B) a colored texture is added to cube, with each UV island having a different color, which is reflected on the cube. In (C) one UV island has been moved to overlap with different colors on the texture, which is reflected on the corresponding side of the cube.

UV maps can also be modified, typically in 3D modeling tools like Blender or using specialized plugins or packages such as UModelerX for Unity. However, even without directly changing the layout of a UV map, knowing the UV layout of a mesh can often be used to directly change the texture in a photo editing software like Gimp or Photoshop. Furthermore, it is relatively easy to export the UV layout of mesh with Blender, resulting in a picture like the UV layout in Figure 9 A, that can be directly imported into any photo editing software and be manipulated like any normal picture, e.g., painting the different island in different colors (Figure 9 B).

Even though UV maps may seem quite unintuitive at first, and the process of creating and editing them in tools like Blender involves a learning curve and can feel tedious, mastering UV mapping opens up many options to modify the texturing of 3D models. As we will see later, it is not just about how the surfaces of our objects are rendered—UV maps are also essential for calculating light and shadows.

UV maps are not required to have a 1:1 aspect ratio (square shape). They can be rectangular or have any proportions. However, square UV maps are often preferred because most textures follow the same aspect ratio.

Texture resolutions

Texture resolutions should always follow the power-of-two rule (e.g., 256×256 or 512×512) since graphics hardware is optimized for such dimensions. While mixed resolutions, like 512×1024 (as long as both dimensions are powers of two), are also supported, non-power-of-two textures can cause performance issues on older hardware and compatibility problems in some applications and result in rendering artifacts. Additionally, power-of-two dimensions are critical for generating mipmaps, which are lower-resolution versions of a texture used to optimize rendering at different distances.

Mipmaps

Not only the geometry of an object but also the patterns on textures can be a source of aliasing. Aliasing in textures occurs when a high-resolution texture is displayed at a reduced size or viewed from a distance, causing fine details to blend improperly. This blending can lead to visual artifacts such as moiré patterns or blurriness. In Figure 10, the left side demonstrates aliasing in the form of moiré patterns, which is not visible on the right side, after enabling mipmaps. This effect happens because the renderer tries to map each texel (the smallest unit of a texture, analogous to a pixel) from the high-resolution texture directly onto screen pixels. When the texture is viewed from a distance or at a shallow angle, multiple texels may correspond to a single screen pixel due to perspective distortion and limited screen resolution. This causes several texels to "compete" to represent the same pixel, resulting in undersampling of details with a high spatial frequency —rapid color or brightness changes in small areas, leading to visible artifacts.

Figure 10. The left side shows a screenshot of a virtual environment without mipmaps for the wall texture. Clear aliasing in the form of a moiré pattern is visible. The right screenshot shows the same environment after generating mipmaps, which effectively removes the aliasing.

Mipmaps usually solve the issue by using lower-resolution versions of a texture as the viewer moves farther away from it. These pre-calculated, smaller textures are automatically applied depending on the distance. Each mipmap level is half the resolution of the previous one, allowing for a smooth transition between levels. For instance, a 256×256 texture generates

mipmaps at progressively lower resolutions, such as 128×128, 64×64, 32×32, and so on, until reaching 1×1.

As explained above, generating mipmaps requires the texture to follow the power-of-two rule. This is because halving dimensions like 256×256 results in clean, uniform steps, avoiding fractional texels. In contrast, a texture with dimensions like 300×300 halves to 150×150 and then 75×75, after which it cannot be evenly reduced further, as individual texels cannot be split into smaller, fractional units.

Mipmaps are also a form of performance optimization. Full-resolution textures are only rendered when viewed up close, while lower-resolution versions are used for distant views where fine detail is not needed.

Fortunately, when working with modern tools like Unreal or Unity, mipmaps do not need to be created manually. Both engines automatically generate them if the texture resolution follows the power-of-two rule. However, aliasing may still occur despite having mipmaps, often due to suboptimal settings. If this happens, adjusting the import settings for mipmaps can help. Both Unreal and Unity allow the application of different filters, such as anisotropic filtering or sharpening, to fine-tune the mipmaps and reduce remaining artifacts.

Color or Base Map

The color map, also called diffuse, albedo, or in Unity Base Map, serves as the foundation for the material's appearance. These maps specify how light interacts with a material's surface in the absence of reflections or other complex effects. For instance, the color map determines whether a table appears as polished wood, painted white, or covered in a patterned fabric. Unlike other maps that define properties like smoothness or metalness, the color map provides the visual detail of the material, such as the grain in wood or the texture of brick. However, the color map alone cannot simulate complex lighting effects but has to be combined with other maps, such as normal or smoothness maps.

Normal Map:

Normal maps simulate surface details like bumps, grooves, and fine textures without adding additional geometry to a mesh. They store the directions of normal vectors — the vectors perpendicular to the surface — from a high-poly model in a form that the map can then be applied to a low-poly model, giving it the appearance of geometric detail even, which is not there.

The process of creating a normal map typically involves a detailed high-poly mesh (Figure 11 A), where the depth and surface details are fully modeled with geometry. This high-poly model is then simplified into a low-poly mesh (C). The surface details from the high-poly mesh are "baked" into a texture (D). Using the normal map on the low poly mesh together with some smoothing can restore almost all the detailed geometric information at a fraction of the computational cost (B).

Although normal maps do have limitations, especially in VR, where stereoscopic rendering and close-up perspectives can reveal the flatness of the surface at sharp angles or extreme viewpoints, the impact of normal maps should not be underestimated.

Normal maps do not always need to be baked onto specific low-poly objects. Instead, textures available on libraries such as AmbientCG.com provide the corresponding normal map for each texture, such as the normal map to simulate the grooves between tiles on the floor. These textures can be easily applied to many objects, without the involving the user in baking normal maps.

Importantly: Many online resources provide two types of normal maps: one for DirectX and one for OpenGL. The key difference is how they handle the green channel (which represents the Y-axis of the normal). In DirectX, the Y-axis points upward, so lighter green shades represent upward-facing surfaces, while darker shades represent downward-facing ones. In OpenGL, this is flipped: lighter green represents downward-facing surfaces, and darker green represents upward-facing ones. This difference can cause lighting to look incorrect if the wrong type of normal map is used. In game engines, Unity typically uses the OpenGL style, while Unreal Engine uses the DirectX style, so it is important to select the right normal map for the engine or convert it if needed.

Figure 11. Illustration of how normal maps preserve visual detail even when geometry is heavily reduced. The upper-left image shows a sculpture with over 1.6 million triangles, while the lower-left version is simplified to around 3,500 triangles, losing much of its fine detail. By applying the normal map (lower right) captured from the high-resolution model, the low-poly sculpture (upper right) regains those fine details.

Metallic

Metal has a distinct appearance because its atoms have free electrons that move easily, allowing metals to reflect light directly and uniformly across a wide range of wavelengths. This property gives metals their characteristic shine and mirror-like effect regardless of their color texture. In physically based rendering, a metallic map is typically a black-and-white texture (Figure 12), where white areas correspond to a value of 1, representing metallic surfaces, while black areas correspond to a value of 0, indicating non-metallic surfaces.

For instance, the painted diamond plate shown in Figure 12 features several areas where the paint has worn away, revealing the bare metal beneath. Using a metallic map allows these

exposed areas to appear metallic, while the painted sections retain the look of painted material.

In principle, grey values between black and white could make a surface appear partially metallic. However, using in-between metallic values creates physically impossible materials since a surface point cannot be partially metal and partially non-metal - it's one or the other. This leads to unrealistic light behavior where the surface partially exhibits both metal and non-metal properties, breaking the physical accuracy that PBR aims to achieve.

Figure 12. Illustration of the effect of metallic maps. In the left, a painted diamond plate is shown with several spots, where the paint has worn off. In the middle, the same diamond plate is enhanced by a metallic map (right side) to add correct metallic reflections.

Smoothness

Smoothness maps allow us to vary the smoothness of a surface using a texture, just like metallic maps, making certain parts appear smoother than others. For example, in Figure 13, a tablet's display is shown with visible fingerprints created using a smoothness map. Smoothness maps are generally useful to add little imperfections to surfaces such as fingerprints, scratches or dirt.

In a smoothness map, white (1) represents a perfectly smooth surface, which reflects light sharply, creating mirror-like reflections. Black (0) corresponds to a completely rough surface, which scatters light diffusely, making it appear matte and non-reflective. Unlike metallic maps, smoothness maps utilize the full range of values between 0 and 1, as real-world surfaces rarely exhibit either perfect smoothness or complete roughness.

It is important to note that Unity uses smoothness maps, whereas other software like Unreal Engine and Blender work with roughness maps. While the underlying concept is the same, the values are inverted: in roughness maps, a value of 1 represents a rough surface, while 0 represents a smooth surface.

Generally, textures sourced from outside the Unity Asset Store, are mostly defined in terms of roughness, making it necessary to invert the color values of the map in an image editing software like Gimp, before importing the map into Unity.

Furthermore, in Figure 8, it might have been noticed that Unity's standard Lit shader does not provide a dedicated slot for smoothness maps but instead provides a slider to adjust the value for the entire material between 0 and 1. However, it is possible to use smoothness maps with the Lit shader. Rather than using a separate texture, the smoothness information is stored in the alpha channel of the metallic map. This means that smoothness and metallic values are

combined into a single texture. The RGB channels define the metallic values, while the alpha channel encodes smoothness.

However, manually adding the smoothness information to the alpha channel of a metallic map can be cumbersome. Fortunately, the process of writing the smoothness information into the alpha channel of the metallic map can be simplified with a Script included in the OpenEnvironments project. In the folder Assets/Editor, there is a script called ImportMetallicSmoothness.cs, which automates this process for the user. The information on how to use the script is described in the script itself.

Figure 13. Illustration of a smoothness map (right) used to add visible fingerprints to the display of a tablet (left).

Ambient Occlusion

Ambient occlusion (AO) maps are grayscale textures that simulate subtle shadowing in areas where surfaces are close together, such as corners and crevices (Figure 14). By darkening regions where ambient light is less likely to reach, AO maps enhance depth and realism, helping to define shapes and spatial relationships. However, because AO maps are baked and static, they do not adapt to dynamic lighting or moving objects, which can sometimes lead to inconsistencies in scenes with changing geometry or light sources. Despite these limitations, AO maps remain a widely used technique, especially for VR rendering, where real-time

techniques such as Screen Space Ambient Occlusion are not an option due to their performance impact and incompatibilities with VR rendering.

Figure 14. This illustration demonstrates the effect of Ambient Occlusion maps in rendering a scene with roofing tiles. The left image displays the roofing tiles without AO, resulting in a flat and less detailed appearance. The middle image shows the same roofing tiles with AO applied, enhancing depth and shadow details between the tiles. The right image presents the AO map used to create these effects.

Opacity

We can also use textures to define which parts of a mesh should be rendered opaque or translucent. Many engines, such as Unreal Engine, provide a dedicated input channel for an opacity mask, a texture that encodes fully opaque areas as white and fully transparent areas as black, with gray values representing levels of translucency in between. While having a dedicated opacity map is convenient, it can be inefficient since opacity only requires a single channel to store values between 0 and 1. Using a full RGB texture for this purpose wastes memory and resources. Instead, opacity can be stored in the alpha channel of another texture—typically the color map—which is how Unity’s Standard Lit Shader handles transparency.

Opacity maps are particularly useful for rendering objects with intricate transparency details, such as frosted glass, meshes with holes (like fences or lace), or partially transparent materials like leaves or decals.

Emission

When using an emissive map, specific parts of an object can be made to glow in a chosen color. For instance, this technique can be applied to make only a lightbulb appear to emit light, while the lamp’s body and lampshade remain unaffected. In Figure 15, a screenshot from the living room scene shows curtains that appear to let light pass through areas that are not obstructed by walls. However, this effect is achieved using an emissive map, rather than actual light transmission. Creating true translucency, such as sunlight shining through fabric,

would require switching the material to "Transparent," which would increase the rendering workload unnecessarily.

Figure 15. The left panel shows the rendering of curtains in front of a window. An emission map (right) was used to illuminate the areas where the sunlight hits the curtains, creating the impression of light passing through the curtains.

Height Map

The standard Lit shader also supports the use of height maps to simulate surface detail (Figure 16). These maps encode grayscale values representing the relative elevation of points on a surface. In Unity and the universal render pipeline, height maps are used for parallax mapping, a screen-space technique that modifies the UV coordinates of textures based on the view angle and the height information. As the camera view angle shifts, parts of the texture appear to move in accordance with the height values stored in the height map, mimicking the way real surface details would become more or less visible from different perspectives.

Figure 16. Comparison of a stone wall texture without a height map (left) and with a height map (right)

Detail Maps

Unity's standard lit shader allows materials to add a second set of textures via the Detail Input fields, enabling the addition of fine details to surfaces. In Figure 17, an example shows how detail inputs can be used to add dirt to otherwise clean floor tiles. Here, a muddy ground texture was used as the Detail Base Map, and a corresponding normal map was added to the Detail Normal Map field.

However, blending the tiles with the muddy ground uniformly would create an unnaturally dirty appearance. Realistically, dirt tends to accumulate more heavily in grooves between tiles, while the tile surfaces show only scattered dirt spots. This effect is achieved using a Detail Mask, which is simply an opacity map, where white areas reveal the detail maps, black areas block them, and gray areas partially show them. In this example, the detail mask ensures the grooves look dirtier, while the tiles display only irregular dirt patterns.

While detail maps enhance realism, they can increase the GPU's workload significantly, if used for several objects, especially when rendering on low-end hardware.

An alternative approach is to pre-blend the detail textures into the base map and the base normal map. With basic skills in image editing software like GIMP or Photoshop, the base and detail maps into a single texture can be combined. Although this method is a bit less flexible than the detail input, it allows to achieve the same visual appearance without increasing the rendering workload at all.

Figure 17. Illustration of how the detail input can be used to add dirt to a tiled floor. (A) shows the clean floor tiles. For the Detail Base input, a texture of muddy ground was used (B). Furthermore, a black-and-white Detail Mask (E) was used to define where the muddy ground should be visible, resulting in the dirty floor tiles shown in (D). The complete shader setup is shown in (C).

Shader Graph

Above we have seen how Unity's standard lit shader can be modified to create a variety of visual effects by manipulating different settings and using texture maps. Going a step further, the shaders for the materials can be defined using custom shaders.

In Unity, surface shaders are traditionally written using a language called ShaderLab, which is Unity's shader language, combined with HLSL (High-Level Shading Language) for the programmable parts of the shader. ShaderLab is used to define the structure and render states of the shader, while HLSL code handles actual computations for vertex and pixel shaders.

However, in this guide, we will not discuss writing shaders in ShaderLab and HLSL and would also not recommend doing so without the necessary experience. Instead, when using the Universal Render Pipeline or the High-Definition Render Pipeline, it is recommended to use *Shader Graphs*.

Shader Graph is a visual tool that allows developers to create shaders without writing code by constructing them via a drag-and-drop node-based interface (Figure 18). Each node in the Shader Graph represents a function or value, and developers connect these nodes to build complex visual effects and material properties. This tool simplifies the process of shader

creation, making it accessible even to those without a deep understanding of programming or shader languages, and it fully integrates with Unity's rendering systems. Unfortunately, the built-in render pipeline does not support Shader Graph.

Below, we will only give a brief overview of shader graphs, but to learn more about using shader graphs, besides many excellent tutorials available on platforms like YouTube, we recommend the “Beginner’s Guide to Unity Shader Graph” by Álvaro Alda, which covers in detail the many ways how shaders graphs can be used to create unique visual effects.

In Figure 18, Unity’s Shader Graph editor is displayed. On the right is the Blackboard, a window that serves as the central hub where all the inputs converge. The Blackboard displays various properties, many of which are familiar from the Standard Lit Shader and allows the direct modification of the properties and variables of each input within the graph. It is divided into two sections: the upper section handles inputs for the Vertex Shader, which can be used to change the shape of the mesh, such as simulating waves by moving vertices periodically up and down of a water surface shader, while the lower "Fragment" section is for the Fragment (or Pixel) Shader. Since most shaders primarily focus on the Fragment section, we focus on its functionality.

Rather than simply modifying hard coded variables, such as color, the Shader Graph allows for dynamic calculations, like blending textures or changing parameters based on object properties. In Figure 18, a simple shader graph is shown that changes the surface color based on the object’s height within the scene. To understand this graph, we begin with the Position node on the left and follow the connections through the graph to the final output in the Blackboard.

The Position node provides the object’s location in different coordinate systems, such as object space or world space. Here, it is set to world space, meaning all calculations relate to the global origin of the scene. The next node, a Split node, separates the position data into its x, y, and z components, represented as R, G, and B respectively (a common convention in shaders). The alpha channel (A) is unused in this context and defaults to 1.0. By selecting the G output, we isolate the y-coordinate, which corresponds to the object’s height in Unity’s world space.

This y-coordinate is then fed into a Lerp (Linear Interpolation) node. The Lerp node blends two inputs (A and B) based on a third input, known as T (commonly referred to as Alpha in other engines like Unreal). A T value of 0 outputs the A input, a T value of 1 outputs the B input, and values between 0 and 1 blend the two inputs proportionally. In this shader, the y-coordinate serves as the T value, while the A and B inputs are two color properties—blue and red. The result of the interpolation is then connected to the Base Color input in the Blackboard.

The effect of this shader is shown on the right side of Figure 18, where the material created from this graph is applied to a sphere. The color of the sphere transitions smoothly from blue at the bottom to red at the top, demonstrating how the shader dynamically changes the surface color based on height in the scene.

Figure 18. Setup of a simple shader graph to change the color depending on the height of a sphere in world space. The shader determines the world position of the sphere using the Position node. The height of the sphere is received by splitting the world position coordinate into XYZ (here RGB) and using the Y (here G) value for the alpha of a linear interpolation (Lerp) node. Parts of the sphere higher than $Y = 1$ will appear in the color defined in "Color1" (here red) and anything with $Y < 0$ appear in "Color 2" (here blue), while anything between 1 and 0 will result in a proportional mix of both color.

Shader Graphs can greatly expand the possibilities for creating a variety of visual effects and can also be used to optimize the rendering performance by enabling certain calculations to be handled efficiently at the shader level, avoiding more expensive operations that would otherwise require additional processing. For example, in the living room scene of the Open Environments project, there is a lava lamp with blue lava flowing inside (Figure 19). The most accurate way to render this effect would involve complex and resource-intensive liquid physics simulations, which are impractical for VR rendering. Instead, the effect was created entirely at the shader level. Rather than simulating volumetric liquid behavior, the dynamic movement and appearance of the "lava" were drawn directly onto the surface of the lamp's glass in 2D, achieving a convincing effect with minimal performance cost.

Often there is no need to develop complex custom shader ideas from scratch. For instance, the lava shader used in the project is largely based on a tutorial found on YouTube (Game Slave, 2023). If there is a specific visual effect in mind, such as water, fire, or glass, a quick online search will uncover countless tutorials. By gaining an understanding of Shader Graph's logic and interface, these existing shaders can be adapted to requirements rather than creating entirely new solutions. This approach is especially valuable in research contexts where commercial novelty is not a priority. Leveraging proven solutions enables the focus to be on achieving results that effectively support the research objectives with greater efficiency.

Figure 19. Screenshot of a lava lamp, part of the “living room” scene in the open environment project.

Decals

Decals are textures projected onto surfaces to add localized details, such as dirt, scratches, or signage. Unlike baking these imperfections directly into the texture of a mesh, decals allow for far greater flexibility, as they can be added, modified, or removed without altering the base texture or model. For example, in Figure 20, a graffiti tag decal is projected onto the surface of a wall without requiring any changes to the wall’s texture or geometry. This makes it much easier to add imperfections without the need to modify or re-export the original assets.

Decals are generally an efficient way to enhance visuals, but excessive use, especially on low-end hardware, can still greatly impact the performance. Decals basically always involve transparency, which leads to overdraw because they are rendered as an additional layer over the existing surface, meaning the same pixels may need to be processed multiple times. Additionally, each decal typically increases the number of draw calls, as they are rendered separately from the base surface.

Similar to the issues with transparency and passthrough mixed reality in general, decals often cause rendering issues when used with passthrough. When a decal with transparency overlaps a mesh, the blending of the decal’s transparency with the underlying surface can conflict with how the passthrough background is composited, causing the underlying mesh to

appear semi-transparent or incorrectly rendered. This happens because the rendering engine may incorrectly interpret or prioritize the alpha blending of the decal.

Figure 20. Using a decal, a texture with a graffiti tag (right side) is projected onto the surface of a wall and blended realistically with the surface.

Material, shaders, and performance

One key optimization, as previously mentioned, involves mipmaps—precomputed lower-resolution versions of a texture. Mipmaps are used when textures are displayed at smaller sizes, reducing aliasing and improving rendering performance. The most critical aspect here, as explained earlier, is that textures must follow power-of-two resolutions (e.g., 512×512 or 1024×1024) to enable mipmap generation.

Mipmaps help by dynamically lowering the resolution of textures when objects are rendered at a distance, preserving detail up close while remaining performance-efficient from afar. This might lead to the assumption that high-resolution textures can be freely used in a scene since mipmaps scale dynamically. While this is partially true for reducing the pixel shader workload, it's important to note that (a) overusing high-resolution textures can still strain resources, and (b) even when a lower resolution mipmap is rendered, the high-resolution versions must still be stored, wasting memory.

To address these issues, texture streaming can be employed. Texture streaming dynamically loads and unloads individual mipmaps from memory as needed, optimizing memory usage. However, if texture streaming is not properly configured it can cause stuttering when the GPU swaps between mipmaps.

Hence, despite the advantages of mipmaps and texture streaming, the best approach to determining the optimal resolution for the textures is to base it on the distance from which they will be viewed and the number of small details the texture has. Textures for objects seen up close should generally be of higher resolution to preserve detail, while lower-resolution textures are sufficient for distant objects where fine details are not discernible.

Another important consideration when selecting texture resolutions is the number of maps combined in the shaders. For example, using only a diffuse and normal map allows for more high-resolution textures in the scene compared to shaders that also incorporate ambient occlusion, metallic, or other maps. Balancing the use of additional maps is essential for maintaining performance while achieving the desired visual quality.

It is also worth noting that not all maps in a shader need to have the same resolution. While mismatched mipmaps can sometimes cause minor visual artifacts, reducing the resolution of less critical maps, such as smoothness or metallic maps, often has minimal impact on overall visual fidelity compared to reducing the resolution of diffuse or normal maps as well.

Lastly, while many texture packs provide a variety of maps, not all of them are necessary to achieve high visual quality. In some cases, certain maps contribute little to no noticeable improvement. For example, with mostly smooth surfaces like polished marble or glass, normal maps often have minimal impact and can be omitted without affecting the overall appearance. Determining which maps to include often requires a bit of trial and error to identify those that meaningfully enhance the visuals and exclude those that do not.

Materials and Draw calls

Earlier, it was explained that the CPU sends draw calls to the GPU to instruct it on what to render on the screen. These draw calls include information about which objects to draw, their colors, textures, and other visual properties. To understand why too many draw calls can have a significant impact on performance, let us set aside CPUs and GPUs for a moment and consider an analogy. Imagine there is a new job, which is to create pictures of geometric shapes painted with watercolor on paper. However, the painting is not being done by the user. Instead, the user can manage a colleague—the painter. The user's responsibilities include preparing everything: mixing colors, selecting brushes, and instructing the painter on what shapes to paint, one after the other.

For example, the first shape is a blue square. To prepare, select the correct brush size, dip it in water, mix the blue paint, and hand the brush to the painter. Then tell the painter the shape, position, and size of the square to paint. Once it is done, take back the brush, clean it thoroughly, and put it away.

Next, the task is to paint a red diamond. The process can be repeated: choose the appropriate brush, dip it in water, mix red paint, and instruct the painter. After that comes a blue circle. Again, clean the previous brush, select a new one, prepare the blue paint, and guide the painter. This process continues until all the shapes are painted onto the paper and then start with the next set.

In this analogy, the time-consuming part is not the painter's work but the preparation—mixing colors, cleaning brushes, and giving instructions. While this scenario is highly simplified compared to real rendering pipelines, it highlights the overhead involved in issuing draw calls. In practice, each call can require changing shaders and textures, or switching other states on the GPU, much like swapping paints and brushes. Although modern systems allow the GPU to

continue drawing while the CPU sets up new instructions, too many calls in quick succession can still overwhelm the CPU side and slow down the entire process.

However, the analogy also highlights possible ways to optimize performance when there are too many draw calls. In the example, the first shape was a blue square, followed by a red diamond, and then a blue circle. If we assume that we do not need to reapply fresh paint for each object of the same color and brush, one way to speed up the process is to group all shapes of the same color and brush and instruct the painter to draw all the blue shapes first, before going over to the next color and brush.

This logic applies to optimizing draw calls in computer graphics as well. By grouping and rendering objects that share the same materials or shaders, we minimize the number of state changes the CPU must manage, thereby improving performance.

Static Batching

Following a similar logic, in Unity we can use a technique called static batching that helps to reduce draw calls. Instead of ordering the render queue, static batching takes all static (non-moving) objects that share the same material into a single mesh at runtime, reducing the number of draw calls to 1. As a result, the GPU can render the scene more efficiently. In order to use static batching, in Unity this needs to be activated on an object level and should always be used for non-moving objects, as it can save significant CPU time.

However, combining objects into a single mesh can increase memory usage and there are limitations to the number and complexity of objects that can be batched together. Furthermore, static batching is not applicable to moving objects as the combined mesh would not update correctly.

Dynamic Batching

Dynamic batching is a technique that automatically combines small, moving objects that share the same material into a single draw call. However, dynamic batching is limited to objects with less than 300 vertices, that share the same material and use compatible shader properties. Dynamic batching can sometimes reduce performance because the process of combining objects into batches is handled by the CPU every frame, which increases CPU workload and overhead. In scenes with many dynamic objects, the additional CPU time spent on batching can outweigh the benefits of reduced draw calls, leading to decreased overall performance.

GPU instancing

Another approach is called GPU instancing, which is a rendering technique where multiple copies of the same mesh can be rendered using a single draw call, but with different positions, rotations, scales, and even different material properties for each instance. The key difference from static batching is that with instancing, there is not a combination with the actual geometry - instead, the GPU is instructed to reuse the same mesh data multiple times with different transformation matrices and properties. Importantly, both static batching and GPU instancing can not be used at the same time. If both are active, Unity will prioritize static batching over GPU instancing.

The choice between these techniques often depends on the specific use case, but we generally recommend using static batching when there is no specific need for GPU instancing. Static batching is easier to implement, works with any shader, and is well-suited for most scenarios involving static objects that do not require individual variations. On the other hand, GPU instancing is ideal when a large number of identical objects need to be rendered, such as vegetation, props, or repetitive architectural elements, and the flexibility to vary properties like colors or other material parameters for each instance is needed.

Texture Atlas

As discussed above, static batching allows for different meshes to be combined as long as they share the same material. For instance, on a dinner table, there might be different meshes for knives, forks, and spoons, all using the same chrome or silver material. The differences between these objects are entirely based on their geometry while the same material is used for each object.

To optimize further, we can use a technique called a texture atlas, which enables different meshes to share the same material while giving each mesh a unique appearance. This method was used in the living room scene to optimize the draw calls for the books on the shelf (Figure 21). While they share identical geometry, they consist of 12 different models, each with unique UV maps. On the right side of Figure 21, there is the texture atlas used for all the books, along with the UV islands for each book. Each UV Island corresponds to a book cover and occupies a distinct area of the texture, such as the evenly distributed rectangles representing the spines of the books. This approach allows each book to have a unique cover design while sharing the same texture and material.

By allocating different parts of the same texture to different objects and ensuring the UV islands do not overlap, we can use a single texture and material for all books while maintaining their distinct appearances. However, this technique does come with some limitations. The UV space allocated to each mesh is reduced when using a texture atlas, which can result in blurry textures if the resolution is not increased to compensate. Additionally, creating or modifying visual properties of individual objects becomes more cumbersome since changes must be made directly to the atlas texture.

Neither Unity nor Unreal provides built-in tools to manipulate UV maps, so creating texture atlases typically requires additional plugins, such as UmodelerX for Unity, or preferably external 3D modeling software like Blender.

Figure 21 also demonstrates how well-laid-out UV maps can make it easy to customize object appearances using image editing software. For example, to change the color of the yellow book in Figure 21, the texture could be opened in GIMP, and the corresponding rectangle located in the atlas, and be either recolored or blended with another texture.

Figure 21. On the left, a rendered image of a bookshelf with several books is displayed. Although the models of the books appear identical, each has a unique UV layout. The right side shows a texture atlas and the distinct UV islands for each book, illustrating that each book is mapped to a different section of the same texture atlas.

Using different Shaders

So far, we have primarily focused on Unity's Standard Lit Shader. While this shader is generally an excellent choice for most kind of surfaces, when developing in low-end systems, relying solely on it can significantly impact performance. Unity provides simpler shader models designed specifically for low-end devices. In the Universal Render Pipeline (URP), this alternative is the "Simple Lit" shader, and in the Built-In Render Pipeline, it corresponds to shaders found under the Mobile category, such as the "Bumped Diffuse" shader. The Simple Lit shader lacks many features of the Standard Lit shader, offering inputs only for color, a normal map, and emission. It omits features like smoothness, resulting in materials that are completely rough with no reflections. Additionally, it does not support metallic or ambient occlusion maps. These limitations reduce the shader's realism, making it less suitable for objects that are visible up close.

However, for surfaces that are naturally rough and non-metallic, such as stone or concrete, the Simple Lit shader can work effectively, even for objects near the viewer. For other objects, the strategy remains the same: use simpler, less expensive shaders for elements that are not visible up close and do not require advanced features like smoothness, while reserving more detailed shaders for objects where realism is critical.

It is also important to note that mixing different shader models increases the workload for the GPU because it must switch between shader models for each draw call. Using a wide variety of shader models in the same scene—something that can easily happen when using custom shaders tailored for specific use cases—can add unnecessary complexity. While combining the Standard Lit shader with the Simple Lit shader, as described above, can improve performance, it is generally best to minimize the number of different shaders in use, sticking to only those necessary for achieving the desired balance of performance and visual fidelity.

We have now covered the basics of materials and shaders. While it is fine to set up materials at this stage, it is important to configure the scene's lighting before fine-tuning material settings. Lighting has a significant impact on how materials appear, and adjusting materials without a basic lighting setup often results in additional tweaks later, as surfaces may look different once the lighting is in place.

This is illustrated in Figure 22, which shows the same scene under three different conditions. In (A), the scene has textures but poor lighting and no shadows, while (B) includes realistic lighting and shadows but features only uniformly grey surfaces. In (C), the textures from (A) are combined with the lighting from (B), demonstrating how dramatically lighting affects the appearance of materials. As can be seen, even though the materials and textures are identical, the surfaces look significantly different in (C) compared to (A). For this reason, it is important to establish the lighting setup first before fine-tuning material settings.

Figure 22. Illustration of the impact of lighting on the appearance of textures: (A) The scene is equipped with textures and objects but suffers from poor lighting, making it appear flat and unrealistic. (B) This version of the scene has been stripped of all textures, displaying a uniform gray shader across all surfaces, but it was enhanced by more realistic light and shadow. In (C) the textures from (A) are combined with the lighting of (B).

Light, Shadow, and Reflections

Now that we have set up the geometry and defined materials for the objects, the next step is to fill the scene with light sources to bring light, shadow, and reflections into play. This process is generally referred to as “lighting.”

Lighting is crucial not only for defining the atmosphere of a virtual environment but often also for enhancing research outcomes. Thoughtfully designed lighting can create specific emotional and cognitive effects, such as calming, neutral, or anxiety-inducing settings. For instance, the color of light influences emotional responses (Mostafavi et al., 2023; Xia et al., 2021) and cognitive performance (Mostafavi et al., 2024).

In addition, consistent and well-balanced lighting on the faces of virtual characters enhances the recognition of emotions (Wisessing et al., 2020), underscoring the importance of proper facial illumination in VR research focused on social interactions.

Perhaps the most significant impact of lighting is its role in determining the visual realism of a scene. Whether an image is perceived as a photograph or a computer rendering heavily depends on the interplay of light, shadow (Rademacher et al., 2001; Wang & Doube, 2011), and reflections. This makes lighting one of the most influential factors in achieving believable and immersive environments. Additionally, the way lighting is configured not only affects realism and visual fidelity but also has a significant impact on the rendering performance of a VR scenario.

Unlike 3D models and materials, which are often available as ready-to-use assets, lighting typically needs to be customized to fit the specific requirements of the project under consideration. Even in prebuilt scenes purchased from asset stores, it is often necessary to adjust the lighting. This might be due to the default setup being too computationally demanding for VR or the addition of new elements, such as stimuli or avatars, which must be integrated into the existing lighting to maintain coherence and realism.

In the following sections, we will first explore the basics of Unity’s lighting system and then discuss how to use these tools to achieve realistic and visually compelling lighting.

Light sources

Unity offers four basic types of light sources, each designed to simulate a different way light behaves in the real world. Understanding the differences in how Unity's light sources emit light is crucial for creating realistic and efficient lighting in the scene.

Directional light: The directional light (Figure 23A), typically included in a new empty scene by default, simulates sunlight by emitting parallel rays in a single direction across the entire scene. The light's position does not affect illumination; only its rotation determines the direction of the rays. Directional lights are ideal for outdoor scenes requiring consistent, large-scale lighting, such as daylight simulation.

Point Light: A point light (Figure 23B) emits rays evenly in all directions from a single point in space. Point lights are commonly used for localized light sources like lamps, torches, or glowing objects. They are particularly effective for illuminating specific areas and creating localized lighting effects without affecting the entire scene.

Spotlight: Spotlights (Figure 23C) emit light in a cone-shaped beam, with the intensity decreasing as it moves further from the source. They are useful for creating focused beams of light, such as flashlight effects, stage lighting, or vehicle headlights and are generally useful for lighting interiors. Spotlights allow developers to control the cone's angle and the falloff of light.

Area Light: An area light (Figure 23D) emits light from a flat surface, such as a rectangle or disk, with rays spreading diffusely rather than in a single direction. This type of light mimics the soft, natural illumination produced by large light sources like windows, screens, or overhead panels. However, a limitation of area lights is that they only support precomputed lighting and cannot be used for real-time lighting.

Figure 23. Illustration of different light sources. (A) shows how a Direct Light illuminates the scene globally from one specific direction. (B) shows a Point Light, which illuminates the scene uniformly in all directions from its origin. (C) shows a Spotlight, emitting the light in a cone shape. (D) illustrates an Area Light, which emits light uniformly in the shape of a rectangle.

Using emissive materials for light

Earlier we showed that materials can be made “emissive” which makes the surface glow, like it was used in Figure 15 to fake light passing through the curtains. However, emissive

materials can not only be used to make surfaces glow but to also emit light into the scene. The shape of the emissive object plays a critical role in determining how the light is distributed in the scene. For example, a flat surface like a screen emits light primarily perpendicular to its surface, while a spherical emissive object emits light more uniformly in all directions. Emissive materials are best employed for visual glow effects and subtle contributions to baked lighting, rather than as primary light sources in real-time applications.

However, emissive materials are not suitable for real-time lighting. While technically possible to make emissive materials emit light in real-time, it requires Enlighten, Unity's deprecated global illumination system. As Enlighten is no longer actively supported or recommended for new projects, it is not discussed in detail here.

Skylight/Ambient light

Ambient light is a fundamental component of real-time rendering that provides the baseline illumination for a scene. While the light sources discussed above always had a specific direction, ambient light is diffuse and scattered, illuminating objects evenly from all directions.

However, ambient light also has notable weaknesses. Because it provides uniform illumination, it tends to flatten the scene if used excessively or without other light sources. This can reduce the sense of depth and realism, making objects appear as though they lack volume or detail. Ambient light by itself does not produce shadows or highlights, which are crucial for defining the shape and texture of objects.

However, it is possible to modulate the ambient light and give it a more natural distribution by using the skybox. Earlier we discussed the use of a skybox in combination with an HDR image to give the participant the impression that the world extends beyond the boundaries of the 3D modeled environment. The same combination can be used to modulate the ambient light. In Figure 24 the same scene is rendered with three different skyboxes. In A) Unity's default procedural sky material was used, while in B) and C) HDR images were used. Look at how each skybox affects the overall luminance of the scene, but also the colors or direction of light and shadow. The HDR images add lots of detail and nuance to the scene, which are missing using the default skybox.

Figure 24. Illustration of the impact of sky texture on the ambient light. In (A) Unity's default procedural sky material, while (B) and (C) use an HDR image for the skybox material. Notice how the light, shadow, and reflections change depending on the material of the skybox.

Real-time light and Global Illumination

Modern game engines provide the tools to calculate light and shadows in real-time, however, the necessary calculations are computationally expensive because every light source requires the engine to calculate how it interacts with the environment, including reflections, refractions, and occlusions.

Light is inherently complex because, in reality, it involves countless photons bouncing off surfaces, refracting, and scattering in all directions. Every surface interaction, even subtle

ones like reflections or soft shadows, adds layers of complexity that our eyes perceive effortlessly but are challenging to simulate digitally. Accurately calculating this in real-time would require immense computational power, making it too costly for real-time VR. Instead, in real-time what we can render is only the so-called direct light (Figure 25A).

Direct light refers to illumination that travels in a straight line from a light source, such as a spotlight creating a bright, localized beam on the wall it is pointed toward. In contrast, indirect light (Figure 24B), also known as Global Illumination (GI), is the light that bounces off surfaces and indirectly illuminates other areas within a scene. While direct light affects only the surfaces it directly touches, indirect light simulates the scattering of light rays throughout the environment, illuminating also the areas of the scene, which are not directly lit.

Although, with real-time ray tracing or with Unreal Engine's Lumen lighting system, there are powerful tools to calculate realistic lighting including GI in real-time. However, these methods are currently still too expensive for VR rendering, especially on standalone HMDs and will not be discussed here further.

Figure 25. Illustration of global illumination. In (A) a Spotlight illuminates the scene without global illumination, leaving the not directly lit parts completely dark. In (B) the same light source is used, but in addition, the global illumination was calculated to simulate the bounce lighting, to illuminate the non-directly parts as well.

Real-time shadows

Comparing the performance profile of both scenes shown in Figure 25, the baked version with global illumination not only delivers more realistic lighting but also outperforms the real-time lit scene. In the baked version, the entire scene requires only 8 draw calls and 63 triangles to render, while the real-time lit scene requires 12 draw calls and a total of 111 triangles. However, neither the number of triangles or objects in the scene changed.

Instead, to create the shadow map for the spotlight, we need to render the scene from the spotlights perspective. As can be seen, four of the four walls of the cube are illuminated, hence these are the objects we need to render twice explaining the increase in triangles to be processed. Furthermore, rendering each real-time shadow issues an additional draw call

for each of the illuminated cubes, explaining the increase of exactly four draw calls. Although the scene is minimalistic, consisting of just five blocks and a single light source—so the performance impact of both versions is negligible—more complex scenes with multiple real-time shadow-casting lights can quickly drain performance. Shadow maps need to be rendered for each shadow-casting light, and the more the illumination of different light sources overlaps, the more vertices and triangles and issue more draw calls have to be processed.

The combination of high rendering cost and missing global illumination can exacerbate the problem, because developers often try to compensate for the lack of indirect light by adding more real-time light sources, frequently with real-time shadows. In many cases, point lights are added to illuminate areas in all directions, unlike the downwards facing spotlight in Figure 25. Since a point light extends in every direction, its shadow map cannot be captured with one pass; instead, a cube map must be created, which involves rendering the scene from six different angles. This approach is like having six spotlights casting shadows at once, significantly increasing the number of draw calls. Even a relatively small scene can start to lose performance on lower-end systems by adding multiple shadow-casting point lights.

Even when lights are set not to cast shadows, a feature that can be easily disabled, they still impose a significant cost on real-time rendering. Each light source contributes to the shading calculations for every surface it illuminates, increasing GPU workload and requiring CPU overhead for managing the lighting data. In VR, where forward rendering is commonly used, the performance cost is particularly demanding as each light's contribution must be calculated for affected surfaces. As more lights overlap in the same area, the calculations multiply linearly, increasing the rendering workload.

Fortunately, most virtual environments are largely static, meaning that the majority of objects and light sources remain stationary. For these elements, lighting conditions can be calculated in advance and stored in textures known as lightmaps. At runtime, the engine uses these lightmaps to display areas of brightness and shadow, eliminating the need to recalculate lighting for static objects on every frame. Instead, the precomputed lighting data is applied consistently, as it does not change. This process of precalculating and storing lighting information is commonly referred to as “baking,” and it will be the focus of the next chapter.

Light baking

Light baking, also referred to as light mapping, involves pre-calculating the lighting and shadow effects in a scene and storing this information in textures called lightmaps. Figure 26 illustrates this process in a simplified manner. In (A), a brick wall is shown in its unlit state, unaffected by any lighting or shadows in the scene—it appears exactly as it would if opened in an image editing tool. When baking light, the system evaluates the scene's light sources and their interactions with objects, creating a lightmap that represents illuminated areas as bright and shadowed areas as dark, as shown in (B), where a spotlight illuminates the wall. At

runtime, this lightmap is blended with the surface of the wall, giving the appearance of dynamic lighting from the spotlight without requiring real-time calculations.

Figure 26. Illustration of lightmaps. In (A), the unlit surface of a wall is depicted. (B) displays the lightmap itself, where brighter areas indicate illumination and darker regions represent shadows. (C) demonstrates the application of the lightmap to the wall, resulting in a bright spotlight casting light and shadows across the surface.

Light baking does not depend on the number of triangles or other similar factors, but rather on the overall size of the surface and the layout of the lightmap UVs (explained below). To improve light baking results, it can be helpful to split large models into smaller pieces, either using a 3D modeling tool or third-party packages for the engine. However, splitting objects can sometimes cause seams where the mesh is divided, especially when baking on the CPU. Hence, if the work is to be carried out using on computer with a decent GPU, always use the GPU for light baking, since it is faster and encounters fewer issues with seams.

Lightmap UVs

Unfortunately, baking the light and shadow into lightmaps is not as easy as dropping lights into a scene and hitting bake. Instead, for light baking we need to prepare our 3D models. In particular, we need to create a second set of UV maps. In the section about shading, we discussed UV maps as coordinate systems that tell the engine how to wrap a 2D texture around a 3D model.

However, instead of using the same UV map that we also use for shading, we need to create a second UV map, so-called lightmap UVs, which need to follow specific rules to work correctly. With respect to shading, we showed that the UV Island can overlap with each other (Figure 9) and the result would still be that the overlapping parts would get the same texture information assign to it.

However, for baking lightmaps, all UV islands need to have their own unique space on the UV map, without other island overlapping with it. The reason is simply that, unless the parts of the mesh which have overlapping UV island, would be illuminated identical, we would try to store lighter and darker parts over each other.

Fortunately, Unity, like other game engines, offers tools to automatically generate this second UV map through the model's import settings. While automatically created lightmap UVs often work well, they may sometimes produce suboptimal results, leading to poor lighting quality.

Importantly, assets from the Unity Asset Store or Epic's FAB often include a secondary UV map specifically for light baking. Before generating new lightmap UVs, check which UV maps are already assigned to the model. In Unity, you can inspect the UV layout by selecting the mesh and viewing its properties in the Inspector—there is an option to preview the UVs and see how many sets are available. Similarly, in Unreal Engine, you can examine the UV maps in the mesh editor window, where the different UV channels are easily accessible.

The UV islands in lightmap UVs must have a small amount of separation, or padding, between them, which has to be defined before generating them lightmap UVs within the engine. During light baking, light and shadow can affect texels just beyond the borders of a UV island. If another island is placed too close, this can result in "bleeding," where the light or shadow from one island unintentionally overlaps with another, causing visual artifacts in the rendered scene.

The required spacing between UV islands depends on the resolution of the lightmap. Higher-resolution lightmaps require less padding in absolute terms, as their finer texel grid reduces the likelihood of bleeding. A general guideline is to maintain at least 2 to 4 texels of padding between UV islands at the target lightmap resolution. Importantly, just like textures used for shading, mipmaps are automatically generated for lightmaps. While this is handled by the engine, it has implications for how much padding is needed. Insufficient padding may look fine at full resolution but can result in bleeding artifacts at lower mipmap levels, as texel data is averaged. Ensuring adequate padding is essential to maintain clean, artifact-free lighting across all viewing conditions.

When generating lightmap UVs in Unity, the lightmap resolution for the object must be specified, and Unity will automatically unwrap the UVs with the appropriate padding based on that resolution. Lightmap resolution can be defined in two ways: globally, affecting the entire scene, or locally, for individual objects. The global resolution determines how many texels are allocated for the lightmap of an object based on its surface size and is defined in texels per unit. The "unit" corresponds to the engine's default unit, which is typically 1 meter. For example, a global lightmap resolution of 40 texels per unit means that a surface measuring 1m x 1m would be allocated a lightmap space of 40 x 40 texels.

Additionally, the lightmap resolution for individual objects can be adjusted using the "Scale in Lightmap" setting. This setting acts as a multiplier for the globally defined lightmap resolution, which is set to 1 by default. At this default value, the object will receive the global resolution, such as 40 texels per unit. Increasing the scale in lightmap to 2.5, for instance, would allocate 100 texels per unit to the object, providing a higher resolution lightmap for that specific model. Conversely, setting the scale to 0.5 would halve the lightmap resolution for the object, reducing it to 20 texels per unit. This flexibility allows the prioritization of higher resolution for objects requiring finer detail while conserving resources on less important elements. Also, typically object with a more complex geometry need higher lightmap resolutions than simple objects, since the lightmap UV cannot be unwrapped as efficiently for more complex objects.

When creating lightmap UVs in Unity, the engine determines the padding distance between UV islands based on the lightmap resolution specified in the import settings. It is crucial that

this resolution matches the actual lightmap resolution used during baking. For instance, if lightmap UVs are generated with a resolution of 40 texels per unit in the import settings but later bake the object at 20 texels per unit, the padding between UV islands will effectively be halved. This discrepancy can lead to light and shadow bleeding, as the reduced padding may no longer be sufficient. To avoid such issues, always ensure that the lightmap resolution set in the import settings corresponds to the resolution used for baking. If the baking resolution is changed after the lightmap UVs have been generated, it is generally advisable to recreate the UVs with the updated resolution to maintain correct padding and prevent visual artifacts. Unreal handles the lightmap resolution a bit more intuitive, as it is defined as a typical texture resolution, such as 256x256, instead of having relative numbers like in Unity.

Furthermore, for accurate lightmap baking, surface parts with significantly different angles should be separated into distinct UV islands. On a cube with 90-degree angles, one side might receive direct light while the adjacent side is shadowed. If these surfaces share UV space in the lightmap, the baked lighting information would blend incorrectly between faces. Separating these surfaces into distinct UV islands ensures proper lightmap generation, preventing light and shadow bleeding between faces with different orientations.

Figure 27 illustrates this concept using the familiar cube from the previous chapter on UV mapping. In (A), the cube is shown as it appears in the 3D scene. (B) displays the UV map used for texturing, where all faces are connected in a T-shape, forming a single UV island. This layout works well for texturing because it minimizes seams and allows for consistent mapping across the cube's surfaces. In (C), the lightmap UVs are shown, with each face separated into its own UV island. These islands are spaced apart with appropriate padding to avoid light and shadow bleeding.

The effectiveness of automatically generated lightmap UVs depends on several factors, including how well the texture UVs were initially unwrapped, the complexity of the model, and its topology—that is, the arrangement of edges, vertices, and polygons that make up the mesh. Simple objects, like the cube in Figure 27, typically result in clean and efficient lightmap UVs. However, for more complex models, the automatic UV unwrapping process often produces inefficient layouts, with excessive unused UV space or too many small, individual UV islands.

While some unused UV space, as seen in Figure 27C, is unavoidable, lightmap UVs should ideally maximize the use of available space on the UV map. This requires a balance between minimizing empty areas and maintaining sufficient padding between UV islands. Models with many small islands suffer from excessive unused space because each island requires padding, which adds up significantly. Additionally, irregularly shaped UV islands make it harder to pack them efficiently, further increasing the amount of unused space on the map.

Figure 27. A) Displays a basic 3D cube. (B) Shows the standard UV map of the cube, where each face of the cube is flattened out to correspond to the 2D texture coordinates. (C) Presents the lightmap UV layout, which is unwrapped differently from the standard UV map in B, with separating the UV islands and leaving a small padding between the island to prevent artifacts light shadow bleed.

Having clean and efficiently unwrapped lightmap UVs is essential for achieving high-quality light baking. While overlapping UV islands must always be avoided, a common workaround for poorly unwrapped lightmap UVs is to increase the lightmap resolution. However, using excessively high resolutions can negatively impact the workflow. The time required to bake lighting depends on factors such as the lightmap resolution, the complexity of the scene, and the hardware being used. While long bake times might be acceptable if baking were a one-time process, finding the right lighting settings is often an iterative task. This involves adjusting settings, tweaking light placement, and re-baking to achieve the desired results. Consequently, lighting will need to be baked multiple times during development. Even small changes to the scene, such as adding or removing objects, require re-baking, and extended bake times can significantly hinder the development workflow.

Additionally, high-resolution lightmaps consume more memory, which can lead to performance issues, particularly in VR or on low-end devices. Each lightmap must be stored in memory, and higher resolutions increase the texture size and memory footprint.

Efficiently unwrapped lightmap UVs not only ensure smoother performance and high-quality lighting but also greatly speed up the workflow. One of the most valuable skills to develop outside of a game engine is learning how to unwrap UV maps using software like Blender. Learning the basics of unwrapping UVs allows the manual refinement of lightmap UVs when engine's tools fall short. Furthermore, mastering the unwrapping lightmap UV also translates to better handling of texture UVs, as the tools and principles are largely the same, apart from some differences in unwrapping rules.

Mixed lighting

Fortunately, light mapping in Unity is not an all-or-nothing approach. Instead, we can combine real-time lighting for movable game objects, such as avatars, with baked lighting for static

objects. When working with mixed lights, Unity offers three lighting modes to define what should be baked and what should remain dynamic.

Baked Indirect: This mode bakes indirect lighting and shadows into lightmaps for static objects, while keeping direct lighting real-time for all objects. It provides a good balance between performance and visual quality. In principle this mode would result in the same performance impact as shown in Figure 24A in the real-time lit environment, with real-time direct shadows, but with the visual fidelity of Figure 24B. Hence, the advantage here would be not a direct reduction of the performance cost over fully real-time lighting, but that we do not need to add additional light sources to fill too dark areas under the ceiling with light.

Shadowmask: The most visually accurate but also most performance-intensive mixed lighting mode. It combines baked indirect lighting with a specialized shadowmask texture that stores high-quality baked shadows for static objects. Dynamic objects receive real-time shadows while static objects use the shadowmask, allowing for complex shadow interactions. However, this comes at the cost of additional memory for the shadowmask texture and increased runtime calculations for blending between baked and real-time shadows. This mode best suits high-end platforms where visual quality is prioritized over performance.

Subtractive: The most performance-efficient mixed lighting mode, as it fully bakes all lighting for static objects into lightmaps. Dynamic objects can receive dynamic from one mixed directional light only, but not from other light sources. This makes this lighting mode particularly interesting for outdoor scene, when the direction light is often the only needed light source providing real-time shadows or for scenarios with do not require real-time shadows.

Each of these modes has distinct memory implications for build size and runtime performance. Baked Indirect typically strikes the best balance, Subtractive offers the best performance but limited flexibility, and Shadowmask provides the highest quality at the cost of performance and memory.

Light Probes

Light probes in Unity capture and store baked lighting information at specific points in a scene, enabling dynamic objects to receive indirect lighting consistent with the environment.

In Figure 28A, copies of the same avatar are shown at varying distances from emissive bars of different colors, illustrating how light probes reflect the surrounding lighting. Figure 28B depicts spheres representing the light probes in the scene, which store precomputed lighting information—such as indirect light and color—for interpolating illumination on dynamic objects. The yellow lines connecting the spheres indicate the interpolation network, showing

how Unity blends lighting information from surrounding probes to compute light at any given point in the scene.

As the avatar moves between light probes, the lighting color and intensity dynamically adjust based on the stored information in nearby probes. Proper placement of light probes is essential; they should be positioned strategically in areas where dynamic objects move to ensure smooth lighting transitions. Insufficient probes can lead to abrupt changes in lighting, while excessive probes may unnecessarily increase complexity and build times. It is important to note that light probes provide illumination but cannot cast shadows.

Figure 28. Illustration of lightprobes. The scene depicts three copies of an identical avatar standing in between differently colored light beams—red, blue, green, and yellow. (A) Shows a network of light probes surrounding the models. Each probe captures lighting information from the environment. In (B) it can be seen how the light color on the avatar changed depending on its position.

Reflection Captures

Reflections in real-time rendering play a crucial role in enhancing the realism and visual fidelity of virtual environments. They can originate from various sources, such as the sky,

surrounding objects, or specifically captured reflection probes that capture the environment's appearance from certain viewpoints.

Real-time reflections, achieved through techniques such as Screen Space Reflections (SSR) enable surfaces to accurately mirror their surroundings in reflections. However, these methods are computationally intensive, rendering them unsuitable for low-end devices where performance resources are limited. Additionally, screen space effects, such as SSR, often conflict with VR rendering—especially in single-pass rendering modes—making SSR suboptimal for most VR applications.

Instead, for VR, reflection capture probes are the better choice. This technique involves strategically placing reflection probes within the environment to capture the surrounding scenery, which are then applied to reflective surfaces to create realistic reflections. Reflection probes work similar to lightprobes. In real-time applications, dynamic reflection probes can update these environment maps in real-time providing reflections that accurately respond to changes in the environment. However, dynamic reflection capture can be resource-intensive, especially in large or complex VR environments with numerous reflection probes. Similar to shadow mapping of point lights, real-time reflection probes require rendering the scene from six viewpoints to create a cube map with maps containing the reflections. Each real-time reflection probe thus increases the number of draw calls and GPU workload, making them too resource-intensive for many VR applications.

Baked reflections are generally preferred for VR rendering as they, like baked lightmaps, precompute and store reflection data, eliminating the need for real-time calculations. However, a key limitation of baked reflections is their inability to update dynamically, making them unsuitable for reflecting moving elements, such as the participant's avatar, which instead remains invisible to reflective surfaces. On the positive side, unlike light baking, baked reflection captures do not require models to be specially prepared or adjusted for applying reflections.

Lighting settings

The Lighting window provides additional settings that significantly impact both the quality of lightmaps and the time required for baking. Unity offers two lightmappers: the Progressive CPU Lightmapper and the Progressive GPU Lightmapper. If the user's computer has a supported GPU, the GPU lightmapper should generally be the first choice, as it is much faster than the CPU lightmapper.

To optimize bake times, disable "Progressive Updates". This feature, enabled by default, allows a view the baking process of individual lightmaps in real time. While this can be helpful for quick iterations—such as refining the bake of a specific object and stopping the process if adjustments are needed—it adds extra workload to the GPU, slowing down the overall bake.

The number of samples used for calculating direct light can also be adjusted, indirect light, and environment (ambient) light. Increasing the sample count improves the quality of baked

lighting but also extends bake times. For most projects, the default settings provide a good balance between quality and baking time.

Unity allows the specification of the number of light bounces, which determines how many times photons reflect off surfaces to generate indirect illumination in a scene. Increasing the number of bounces results in brighter indirect light, as more reflections contribute to the overall lighting. However, with each bounce, the light's energy decreases due to absorption and scattering, meaning subsequent bounces have progressively less impact both visually and computationally.

The first 2–3 bounces significantly affect both bake times and visual quality, as they provide most of the indirect lighting. Beyond that, the Progressive Lightmapper optimizes for diminishing returns, making additional bounces less computationally impactful and visually noticeable. As a result, exceeding three bounces is rarely necessary.

Unity's lightmapper applies filters to lightmaps to smooth artifacts and correct inaccuracies. Filtering is essential for reducing noise, especially in low-light or high-indirect illumination areas. While the "Auto" setting dynamically adjusts filters and typically provides excellent results, different filters can be manually tweaked and selected. However, for most cases, sticking to "Auto" is recommended.

The default lightmap resolution in Unity is 40 texels per unit, which is relatively high and can lead to long bake times and large lightmaps, especially in bigger scenes. For well-optimized lightmap UVs, it's often better to start with a lower resolution, such as 10 texels per unit or less, to bake the scene and evaluate the overall lighting. Some objects may display noticeable artifacts, while others might already look acceptable. Afterwards the resolution can be increased globally, while reducing the "Scale in Lightmap" setting for object which look fine. For example if the global resolution is increased by 2, the individual objects without artifacts can be changed to 0.5. Alternatively, for objects with poor results, their scale in lightmap setting could be increased while keeping the global resolution the same. Iterating between adjusting the global resolution and individual object settings helps achieve an optimal balance of quality and performance.

Next, we can adjust the lightmap padding. Similar to the lightmap UVs of individual objects, padding is required between the UV islands allocated to different objects to prevent bleeding artifacts. Usually, leaving the default provides good results.

After baking the lighting, selecting a static object in the editor will display its lightmap in the Inspector. Double-clicking on the lightmap will expand it. An example lightmap is shown in Figure 29. It is important to note that lightmaps are not generated individually for each object; instead, Unity combines the multiple objects into as few lightmaps as possible to optimize memory usage. The blue lines represent the edges of the UV islands for several objects in the scene. Repeating UV patterns correspond to the lightmap UVs of identical copies of the same mesh.

The lightmap of the selected object is highlighted in yellow. Visually inspecting lightmaps can help identify whether poor bake results are due to a low lightmap resolution or poorly unwrapped lightmap UVs. If an object with poor bake results occupies only a small fraction of the lightmap, it means that the "Scale in Lightmap" setting should be increased. Conversely, if the object already occupies a significant portion of the lightmap, the issue is more likely related to suboptimal UV unwrapping, and improving the lightmap UVs would yield better results.

Figure 29: Baked lightmap. The blue lines represent the lightmap UVs of several objects in the scene. The texture below is the lightmap used for these objects. In yellow highlighted is the portion of the lightmap used by the selected objects in the inspector.

In the Lighting window (Figure 30), the maximum size of a single lightmap can be defined, which is set to 1024 by default. Reducing this size results in more individual lightmaps being created. Since lightmaps are textures, increasing the size from 1024 x 1024 to 2048 x 2048 increases the total capacity by four times, which can reduce the number of individual lightmaps required for baking by up to four times, albeit increasing the memory usage per lightmap.

This setting does not directly impact the quality of the light bake but establishes an upper limit for the resolution. The lightmap resolution for any object cannot exceed the maximum size of a single lightmap. If an object's lightmap resolution exceeds this limit, Unity automatically uses the highest possible resolution within the defined maximum lightmap size. However, the light baking can influence the number of draw calls. When multiple objects share the same material and are eligible for batching, they can be rendered together in a single draw call. However, if different lightmaps are assigned to these objects, Unity treats them as distinct, leading to separate draw calls for each object. Hence, adjusting the maximum lightmap size can influence how efficiently Unity packs lightmap UVs. A larger lightmap size allows for more UVs to be packed into a single texture, potentially reducing the number of lightmaps and associated draw calls. On the other hand, especially low-end GPUs can often handle smaller texture more efficiently and in small scale scenes, as they are often

used in research contexts, the draw call impact from having more but smaller lightmaps will most likely not evolve into a major performance bottleneck. Setting the maximum lightmap size to 2K typically provides sufficient space for large, detailed, or challenging objects to bake correctly and to pack lightmaps efficiently, while still being manageable for lower-end systems, such as standalone VR headsets.

By default, Unity compresses lightmaps to reduce their overall size, but this can sometimes introduce unwanted artifacts. Uncompressed lightmaps avoid these issues but can quickly consume large amounts of memory, especially in larger scenes or when using suboptimal lightmap UVs. For this reason, lightmap compression is generally recommended. Unity offers various compression quality settings, ranging from low to high. High-quality compression provides the best visual fidelity but achieves the least reduction in size, while low-quality compression minimizes size at the cost of visual quality. For small, interior environments, such as a single room, high compression quality is usually safe to use, even on standalone VR systems. In contrast, larger environments may benefit from stronger compression to balance memory usage and performance.

We already discussed Ambient Occlusion, which is that areas of an object that are self-occluded or near other surfaces appear darker due to limited exposure to ambient light. For example, in an indoor room, corners where the ceiling meets the walls are typically slightly darker than the center of the walls or ceiling. Unity allows Ambient Occlusion to be baked directly into lightmaps.

The ray length used to determine where occlusion occurs and shadows are added can be controlled. Larger ray lengths result in more pronounced Ambient Occlusion effects, as they extend the area considered for occlusion. Additionally, the contribution of Ambient Occlusion to direct and indirect lighting can be adjusted. Excessively strong Ambient Occlusion settings can lead to overly dark corners and self-occluding areas, where shadows may look more like dirty smudges than natural shading.

There are two types of lightmaps in Unity: directional and non-directional. Both store overall brightness and color in one map, but directional lightmaps include an additional map to store the direction of the light. This directional data allows the shading of a surface to respond to the underlying normal map. This makes details like grooves, bumps, and textures appear more realistic as they react to lighting changes in a believable way. However, this comes at the cost of increased memory usage and added runtime overhead. Non-directional lightmaps, on the other hand, are more lightweight, as they store only require a single map. However, the lack of directional data means surfaces will not interact with normal maps or exhibit detailed shading effects, resulting in flatter and less dynamic lighting. Typically, directional lightmaps are preferred for their higher visual fidelity. With optimized lightmap UVs and a reasonable overall lightmap size, they usually do not pose a significant performance bottleneck, even in medium-sized scenes running on latest generation of standalone VR systems.

Albedo Boost is a setting in Unity that artificially brightens or intensifies the base color (albedo) of the materials. For realistic rendering, this setting should ideally remain at 1, as this default value ensures physically accurate reflections of color on the surface. Adjusting the Albedo Boost deviates from this accuracy, resulting in lighting that no longer behaves realistically.

Figure 30. Lighting Settings window in Unity, where users can configure various lighting settings.

Lighting the scene

Now that we have prepared all static objects for which we want to bake light, it is time to add light sources to the scene.

One of the first steps when setting up lighting is to replace Unity's default skybox material with an HDRI. Using an outdoor daylight HDRI always includes a light source direction based on position of the HDRI at which the sun is shown. It is crucial to align the directional light in the scene with the light direction of the HDRI; otherwise, the shadows and lighting from the directional light will appear incongruent with the sunlight defined by the HDRI. For Unity's default skybox and some procedural skyboxes, the directional light can be linked to the skybox, automatically updating the skybox based on the light's rotation. However, this functionality does not apply to HDRIs, so the directional light's rotation will need to be adjusted to match the sun's position in the HDRI.

When working on a typical interior scene, adding only a directional light and a skybox is usually insufficient to properly illuminate the space, as this approach often leaves the interior too dark unless the skylight is overexposed. To achieve realistic lighting, interiors should include a mix of artificial light sources. In the chapter on geometry, we discussed the importance of adding props like lamps or ceiling lights to represent light sources. These props will now serve as the basis for placing Unity's light sources.

The next step is to add a combination of area, point, and spotlights to simulate light coming directly from these props. Reference images of similar lamps are helpful here, as they provide example into how light is distributed, including its direction, intensity, and shadowing. Using these references, position and configure the light sources near the props to replicate the lighting behavior as closely as possible.

This approach is essential for two reasons. First, Unity's light sources emit light but are themselves not visible in the rendered scene. To create a believable environment, each light source should have a realistic origin, such as a ceiling fixture or a table lamp, rather than simply being placed invisibly in the scene.

The other reason follows the simple logic: if the scene is populated with props like lamps, TV screens, or other objects that emit light in reality, and their placement and distribution are realistic, all that is required is to add light sources to these props to mimic how they would emit light if they were real.

While engines like Unity or Unreal offer only a few basic light types—such as point and spotlights for real-time and baked lighting, and area lights or emissive materials for baked lighting—these can be used creatively to simulate a wide variety of light emission patterns. For indoor environments, a combination of these light types is typically sufficient to recreate the way most real-world light sources behave.

For example, in Figure 31A, see a room with two long neon tube lights mounted on the ceiling is shown. Unity doesn't have a built-in light source that perfectly replicates the way these tubes emit light. However, because the number of fully baked light sources don't affect runtime performance—though they can increase bake times—we can creatively simulate the effect. In Figure 31B, 30 spotlights were used for each neon tube, positioned along the length of the tubes to cover almost their entire surface. Each spotlight is set to a wide angle but with low intensity, creating the impression of continuous light emitted by the tubes, even though it is achieved with multiple discrete light sources.

In Figure 31C, a small table lamp is shown. While it might seem logical to use a point light for this type of light source, point lights offer limited control over what gets illuminated and often result in less realistic lighting (for example, light might spill onto areas that should remain dark). Instead, two spotlights were used here: one facing downward and another upward. The radius of each spotlight were adjusted to match the different angles and amounts of light emitted toward the top and bottom of the lamp.

A typical use case for point lights is illustrated in Figure 31D, where a red point light was added to simulate the light emitted by a fireplace. However, point lights are rarely suitable as the primary light source for an interior space, as real-world light sources rarely illuminate uniformly in all directions. The exception might be a traditional lightbulb suspended at eye level. To limit the range of illumination from a point light, it can be placed within a 3D model that restricts the light to a specific opening. However, working with spotlights is generally easier, and if the light source casts real-time shadows, spotlights are also more efficient. For most visible light sources in the scene, spotlights are a versatile and efficient choice, offering better control and realism than point lights in the majority of cases.

Figure 31. This illustration demonstrates the application of various light sources to create realistic lighting in 3D scenes: (A) Displays an office setting illuminated by two long neon tube lights. (B) Reveals the actual light sources used to simulate the neon tubes' effect in the same office scene by a large number of individual spotlights. (C) Features a small table light, where two spotlights are positioned to mimic the light it emits. (D) Shows a red point light used to replicate the glow from a fireplace.

Once the scene is replete with light sources and configured the lighting settings, it is time to bake the scene. As mentioned earlier, it is a good idea to start with a low lightmap resolution to test the overall setup. This will help identify which objects look acceptable with a lower resolution and which require a higher lightmap resolution to achieve better results. Objects with intricate geometric details often require a higher lightmap resolution because their complex UV layouts make it harder to use the available UV space efficiently.

Also, even at low resolution, baked lighting can provide a clear sense of the scene's overall brightness as well as the emission pattern and shape of each light source. After baking, it may be the case that direct lighting from a source is too bright or too dim, or that indirectly lit areas are too dark. To address these issues, the contribution of both direct and indirect lighting can be adjusted, either for individual light sources or globally. For instance, if the entire scene appears too dark, the global indirect lighting intensity in the Lighting window can be increased and baked again. Similarly, boosting the skybox intensity can brighten the environment, but the skybox contribution should generally not exceed a value of 1, as higher values can create an unnatural, overly bright appearance and reduce realism.

If only specific areas of the scene are too dark, increasing the intensity or indirect contribution of the light sources in those regions can help. Balancing these settings often involves trial and error to achieve the desired result. By iteratively adjusting light intensities, contributions, and resolutions, the lighting can be refined to create a visually cohesive and realistic scene.

Post Processing

Postprocessing refers to a variety of visual effects applied to the final image after the main rendering process is complete. These effects can enhance the visual appearance of a scene by simulating camera and film-like effects such as bloom, depth of field, motion blur, and color grading. By modifying the rendered image at this stage, postprocessing allows developers to achieve complex visual results without increasing the complexity of 3D geometry or materials. The concept is similar to applying filters in tools like GIMP or Photoshop, but in real-time for rendered frames. While postprocessing can significantly enhance the aesthetic appeal of a scene, it also comes with a notable performance cost.

Postprocessing is computationally expensive because it operates on the entire rendered image in screen space, meaning the effects are applied to every pixel on the screen rather than targeting specific objects or regions. For instance, the Meta Quest 3 combines roughly 9.1 million pixels across both displays. After completing the primary rendering, these 9.1 million pixels must be processed again for postprocessing, adding a substantial workload. These pixels are often not just processed once—effects as bloom (see below), require multiple passes that repeatedly read from and write to the image.

Postprocessing should only be applied once the scene is fully developed and optimized. When adding postprocessing effects, it is important to enable them one at a time and test their impact on the visual appearance and the rendering performance.

One postprocessing effect that greatly enhances visual realism is bloom, which creates a glowing halo around bright light sources. In Figure 32, compare the same scene with and without bloom: on the left, the scene lacks bloom, and on the right, bloom has been applied. Notice how the neon tubes on the left appear as regular light sources, while on the right, the tubes look as though they are actually emitting light due to the bloom effect. Bloom can significantly increase the believability of light in a scene, but it is important not to overuse it. Too much bloom can make light sources overly bright and distracting. A subtle amount,

however, can be enough to make a light source appear naturally luminous without overwhelming the scene.

Figure 32. Shows an office scene without bloom (left) and with bloom (right) added. Notice how the light on the right shows glowing, which is missing on the left.

The color adjustment filter, which offers a variety of settings for altering the overall color grading of the scene, can be useful for correcting the brightness and color of the illumination in the scene. One key adjustment is light exposure, which allows making of the scene brighter or darker. The advantage of using the exposure adjustment is that the brightness of the scene can be adjusted in real time without having to bake the scene again. The light exposure can be used to create fade-out and fade-in effects by gradually reducing it to zero and then restoring it to its original value. This technique is useful for smooth transitions between virtual environments and can be implemented easily with a simple script.

Another postprocessing effect that can improve the visual appearance is tone mapping. Tone mapping adjusts the scene's brightness and contrast to mimic how light is perceived by the human eye, ensuring that details in both dark and bright areas of the scene are visible.

However, considering the performance overhead, the goal should ideally be to achieve the correct brightness and light colors in the scene through the lighting setup itself, such as adjusting the intensity and color of lights or controlling the contribution of direct and indirect lighting. These adjustments come with little to no additional computational cost, unlike postprocessing effects.

By using postprocessing, a vignette effect can also be applied to the field of view. A vignette darkens the outer edges of the screen, focusing attention toward the center. This effect is commonly used in VR applications to reduce peripheral vision, which helps minimize the

perception of motion. Our peripheral visual system is particularly sensitive to movement, and in VR, contributes to simulator sickness. By darkening the peripheral field of view, the vignette reduces the amount of visually perceived motion, which can help mitigate simulator sickness (Buhler et al., 2018).

In addition to the post-processing effects discussed, Unity and Unreal offer several other post processing effects and filter that are typically used for artistic purposes rather than realism. These effects, such as adding fine TV grain or applying color filters like sepia, are often aimed at creating a “movie” or “film” look, rather than enhancing realism. For instance, depth of field can be used to simulate focus, where objects at a certain distance appear sharp while those closer or further away become blurred, giving the scene a photographic feel. While this can improve the realism of still images, it does not translate well to VR and might instead cause discomfort for the participant.

In summary, while postprocessing can significantly enhance visual quality and realism, it comes with a considerable performance cost and should be used sparingly. If the performance allows it, bloom is often the most important postprocessing effect, as it makes light sources appear as if they are actually emitting light. Other postprocessing effects either provide artistic enhancements or serve as visual corrections, many of which can often be achieved through proper material or lighting settings.

Importantly, due to differences in the rendering pipeline, postprocessing does not work when rendering a mixed reality application using passthrough cameras. This is because the passthrough camera feed is typically handled separately from the rest of the scene. However, some platforms, such as Meta Quest, do provide a limited set of custom postprocessing effects specifically designed for mixed reality applications. These effects allow developers to adjust certain visual aspects, like contrast or brightness, within the mixed reality feed, but they are not as versatile or powerful as the full range of postprocessing effects available in traditional rendering pipelines.

User Interfaces

One often overlooked aspect of achieving visual realism is the design of user interfaces (UI), such as buttons. A common approach is to display a floating UI panel with two-dimensional buttons, typically using rays to interact with these buttons (i.e., pointing a virtual beam at them to select and press elements at a distance). This kind of UI is easy to implement but certainly not realistic, as we are not surrounded by floating panels in everyday life. While that may change if mixed reality systems such as Apple's Vision Pro or Meta's Orion become widely adopted, for now, these floating interfaces combined with ray interactors do not represent how people interact with the real world. Instead, user interfaces are embedded into physical objects or surfaces. As an example, instead of using a hovering 2D interface, developers can create simple mechanical buttons that mimic the up-and-down movement of their real-world counterparts when pressed, combined with haptic feedback. However, there are circumstances in which a 2D interface remains preferable, especially when numerous options or buttons are needed. In these cases, realism can still be maintained by placing the interface

on a virtual display, such as a tablet (Figure 33), rather than letting it float in mid-air. When the tablet is within reach, participants can rely on poke interactors, which allow them to tap the on-screen buttons with their fingertips, much like they would on a physical tablet. This approach situates the interface in a believable context, ensures that interactions feel more intuitive, and is often easier to explain to participants compared to the relatively unfamiliar ray interactor method.

Figure 33. Screenshot of a virtual tablet with three buttons to select the language. The button uses poke interactors, which allows the participant to simply tap in the button to press them.

Profiling

In the introduction we pointed out that real-time rendered environments must run on systems with limited performance, meaning the GPU and CPU have finite resources for rendering. Every addition to the scene consumes a portion of these resources. Therefore, to create visually stunning yet well-optimized virtual environments, it is crucial to understand the impact that various visual effects and additions have on performance. While poor performance and frame drops are clear issues, an over-optimized environment can hinder the realism of a study, limiting its potential. Even for experienced developers, finding the perfect balance between performance and visual fidelity can be challenging during development, as it is not always easy to choose the ideal settings and assets.

This is where profiling becomes essential. Profiling refers to the process of systematically analyzing performance metrics to locate potential bottlenecks and ensure the application maintains the target frame rate across all conditions.

While applications with severe frame drops can often be quickly identified by simply putting on the HMD and checking for stuttering while looking around, it is not a reliable method for accurately assessing the applications performance. When frame drops occur, VR runtimes like

SteamVR or Meta Quest often reduce the scene's frame rate—sometimes by half—and apply correction mechanisms to the head rotation to smooth out perceived lag. As a result, the experience may feel more stable than it actually is, masking underlying performance issues.

Another intuitive but slightly more reliable method for testing performance is to wave the hand left and right. Assuming solid hand tracking, the movement of the hand should be smooth. If there is a noticeable lag in the hand movement, it is usually a clear sign of frame drops, as the smoothing of head rotations does not apply to hand tracking, making any delays more visible.

While this hand-waving test can give a quick, basic sense of whether the application is experiencing frame drops, it should be viewed as a preliminary check with limited reliability. First, it depends on the smooth tracking of the hands and tracking problems could be mistaken for frame drops. Second, while it can indicate if the application is lagging, it does not provide detailed information about the extent of the performance issues. For example, the application could be dropping frames, but the GPU workload might only be marginally higher than its capacity, or the workload could be significantly beyond what the GPU can handle. It also does not reveal whether the application is CPU-bound or GPU-bound, which is crucial information for identifying the root cause of the problem. Knowing whether the bottleneck is in the CPU or GPU helps narrow down potential causes. CPU-bound performance issues might stem from expensive tasks like physics simulations or complex AI, while GPU-bound issues are typically related to rendering tasks, such as real-time shadows, texture resolutions, or complex shaders.

Profiling tools are integrated into most game engines and provide a range of metrics, including frame times, CPU and GPU usage, memory consumption, and the number of draw calls. Unity also offers a *Stats* window, which displays real-time data on batches (draw calls), triangles, and vertices. Unreal Engine provides a similar set of information. Console commands such as `stat fps`, `stat unit`, and `stat render` can be used to display real-time statistics on frame rate, CPU time, and GPU time.

However, while the profiling tools within the engine's editor provide useful insights during early development, they do not reflect actual performance on the target VR device. Profiling must always be conducted on a standalone build—e.g., an APK for Android or an .exe for Windows—independently of the engine's editor.

Furthermore, in the case of standalone headsets like the Meta Quest, profiling must be done directly on the device itself. Using tools like Quest Link is not suitable for this purpose, as it renders the VR scene on the PC's GPU. This does not reflect the performance of the final standalone experience.

Fortunately, both PC VR and standalone VR systems provide tools to test their performance under optimal conditions. For instance, SteamVR includes a profiler under "Advanced Frame

Timing," which quickly provides detailed information about GPU usage, CPU usage, memory consumption, and more.

For standalone HMDs like Meta and Pico, the companies offer profiling tools such as the OVR Metric Tools for Meta devices. These tools run alongside the application and display a simple overlay, providing real-time information on various performance metrics.

Figure 34 shows a screenshot of the OVR Metric Tools overlay. One of the key metrics is the number of "stale frames", which refers to frames that did not complete in time, essentially counting frame drops. Ideally, in an optimized application, this number should be zero. The opposite of stale frames is "early frames", where the GPU finishes rendering much earlier than needed. While early frames generally indicate that the application is running smoothly and rendering ahead of schedule, having too many early frames may suggest that unused resources are available, which could be used to enhance the visual fidelity of the scene.

The overlay also provides real-time information on both GPU usage (GPU U) and CPU usage (CPU U), which can help determine whether a lagging application is CPU-bound or GPU-bound. CPU-related issues typically arise from heavy game logic, complex physics calculations, or too many draw calls and script executions per frame. GPU bottlenecks, on the other hand, are often caused by high-resolution textures, demanding shaders, extensive post-processing effects, or an excessive number of polygons, which can lead to overdraw and a high per-pixel workload.

Figure 34. Example overlay of the OVR Metric tools with various information about the rendering performance, such as CPU and GPU workload.

In the following, we will explain how to use the OVR Metric Tools and similar tools to identify performance problems in the VR application. While the specific information provided may vary slightly between profilers and platforms, the general approach and procedure are consistent across different tools.

The most immediate information about the performance is the framerate, which should be at the target frame rate, such as 72FPS. If the target frame rate is not constantly met and there are "stale" frame (i.e., frame drops) one of the first steps is to monitor GPU usage (GPU U) and CPU usage (CPU U). If the CPU is the limiting factor, optimization efforts should focus on reducing draw calls, simplifying physics calculations, or minimizing computational

overhead from scripts. If the GPU is the bottleneck, the focus should be to reduce shader complexity, lowering texture resolutions, or simplifying scene geometry. Knowing which component is the performance bottleneck is critical to applying the correct type of optimization.

However, even if the application seems to run well and the workload of the CPU and GPU stay under 99% all the time, it is important to explore the entire virtual environment. Often certain elements in a scene are especially taxing and without testing the entire virtual environment, might be overlooked. During profiling, move through the environment, interact with different objects, and examine various areas while closely watching the metrics. This will help identify if certain objects or parts of the scene are causing performance spikes.

For example, if large textures appear on screen, there may be a sudden increase in GPU usage. This could indicate that the texture size is too large. To confirm, try reducing the texture sizes or using lower-resolution textures and observe whether GPU or CPU usage drops and headroom improves. A noticeable improvement would suggest that the texture size was indeed overloading the rendering pipeline. If CPU usage spikes when they enter parts of the scene with many objects visible at once—regardless of their complexity—it may indicate an issue with the number of draw calls being made.

Another important metric to keep an eye on in the OVR Metrics Tool is memory usage. Although performance bottlenecks typically manifest as high CPU or GPU usage, observing the memory usage while looking through the scene can for example reveal if some parts of the scene contain an overly high number of high-resolution textures.

Throughout this testing, it is crucial to interact naturally with the environment rather than simply letting the camera remain in one place. Looking in all directions, moving around, and triggering various in-game events will reveal the conditions under which CPU or GPU usage spikes and frame timing becomes unstable. If missed frames coincide with the moment the participant glances toward a large complex structure or steps into a densely populated area, that immediately narrows down where to investigate further. By combining these real-time observations with changes in CPU and GPU metrics, a better idea for deciding whether to optimize textures, reduce draw calls, or implement other changes aimed at preserving stable frame performance in VR, is gained.

The metrics provided by OVR Metric Tools and other profiling tools are extensive and too detailed to cover in full here. However, HMD manufacturers typically provide documentation on the various metrics available (e.g. for the OVR Metrics app detailed explanation can be found here: <https://developers.meta.com/horizon/documentation/unity/ts-ovrstats/>).

In addition to the real-time metrics provided by tools like OVR Metric Tools, both Pico and Meta offer advanced profiling tools, such as the Pico Performance Profiler and Meta's OvrGpuProfiler, which provide deeper insights into GPU performance. These tools collect more detailed GPU data beyond what is available in the OVR Metrics Tool, offering a closer look at hardware-specific bottlenecks. Unlike real-time tools, OvrGpuProfiler records data during the VR session and allows to analyze it after data collection.

While the detailed information from these profiling tools can be valuable, it may be overwhelming without the expertise to interpret it. For most VR applications developed for research—which are typically smaller in scale and optimized for a specific device—tools like OVR Metric Tools are usually sufficient for identifying common performance bottlenecks. However, if these tools fail to uncover the issue, more advanced profiling tools may offer deeper insights.

For more in-depth analysis, RenderDoc is a powerful tool that hooks into the rendering process to analyze the composition of a single frame. It can extract and summarize every rendering step, including textures, shaders, material settings, and vertex counts. Most importantly, it provides detailed timing information for each rendering step. However, like the profiling tools provided by Meta and Pico, RenderDoc can be excessive without the technical expertise needed to interpret the data effectively.

Discussion

This guide has sought to bridge the gap between the technical complexities of real-time, realistic rendering and the practical needs of researchers in the human sciences. By detailing the foundational concepts—from shader workflows and draw call management to the intricacies of lighting and asset integration—we have provided a roadmap for designing immersive VR environments that are both visually compelling and performance efficient.

We hope that this guide serves as both a reference and an inspiration, empowering researchers to leverage realistic VR scenarios to deepen experimental insight and foster innovation across diverse fields.

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